

Congestion-aware pick-up and drop-off network design problem

Santiago Álvarez-Ossorio Martínez ^b,
Klaus Bogenberger ^a

^a Chair of Traffic Engineering and Control, Technical University of Munich, Arcisstr. 21, 80333, Munich, Germany

^b Professorship of Mobility Policy, Technical University of Munich, Arcisstr. 21, 80333, Munich, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Mobility-On-Demand (MOD) services have been shown to increase traffic congestion, primarily due to the rise in total Vehicle-Kilometers-Traveled. Additionally, frequent short-term stops for passenger Pick-Up and Drop-Off (PUDO) processes further disrupt traffic flow and reduce network capacity. With vehicle automation expected to boost demand for such services, large segments of the transport network could be critically affected by both Autonomous MOD (AMOD) vehicle movement and PUDO activities.

This study introduces a novel strategic planning problem for an AMOD service with walking legs, which involves deciding where and how much curb space should be dedicated for PUDO processes and where to prohibit double parking PUDOs. We formulate a multi-objective optimization problem with three goals: minimize traffic congestion, reduce walking times for AMOD users, and limit curbside space consumption. We propose a modular approach with three components: i) an AMOD model with PUDO location and regulation constraints, ii) a static traffic assignment with sensitivity to PUDO frequencies per link, and iii) an upper-level optimization that employs the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (ALNS) metaheuristic to identify (near-)optimal PUDO regulation strategies.

A case study on a small urban network highlights the importance of accounting for the effects of PUDO processes on the traffic system. The findings suggest that at low AMOD penetration, dedicated PUDO areas may be unnecessary with limited system-wide cost, whereas at higher penetration rates, curbside provision yields significant benefits, e.g., under a 7.5% AMOD demand, allocating 100 strategically placed curbside spaces raises average network speeds by 2 km/h compared to allowing double parking only.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the widespread availability of internet connectivity and mobile technologies has fueled the rapid expansion of Mobility-On-Demand (MOD) services, such as Uber, Lyft, and Didi, transforming urban mobility by offering flexible, user-centric alternatives to conventional transport modes.

MOD services present a diverse array of social and economic impacts. Many of these are viewed positively: they are convenient for the users and adapt to their specific travel needs, particularly benefiting older adults and individuals with mobility limitations,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: santiago.alvarez@tum.de (S. Álvarez-Ossorio Martínez), florian.dandl@tum.de (F. Dandl), allister.loder@tum.de (A. Loder), klaus.bogenberger@tum.de (K. Bogenberger).

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and they enhance accessibility in areas underserved by public transit. Furthermore, MOD services are often cited for their potential to reduce private vehicle ownership, alleviate on-street parking demand, and complement existing public transport systems (Shaheen et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2022), although some of these claims have been challenged by empirical evidence (Diao et al., 2021; Erhardt et al., 2022). Conversely, numerous studies have identified negative externalities associated with MOD services, including the rise in vehicle kilometers traveled (VKT), increased traffic congestion, and associated environmental impacts—primarily driven by fleet rebalancing, empty-vehicle trips, and induced demand (Erhardt et al., 2019; Oh et al., 2020). To a certain extent, these adverse effects can be mitigated by modifying operational aspects of the services or implementing regulations. For example, combining several requests into a ride (i.e., ride-pooling) has been shown to reduce VKT and enhance system efficiency compared to ride-hailing services (Hyland and Mahmassani, 2020). Similarly, asking passengers to walk to designated stop locations rather than offering a door-to-door service has demonstrated positive operational, environmental, and traffic-related impacts (Stiglic et al., 2015; Zwick et al., 2021; Engelhardt and Bogenberger, 2021; Fielbaum et al., 2021; Gurumurthy and Kockelman, 2022).

A unique feature of MOD vehicles compared to regular traffic is that they perform frequent short-term traffic stops for passenger pick-up and drop-off (i.e., PUDO processes). These typically occur either at the curbside (using dedicated bays, similar to taxi stands, or regular parking spots) or directly on the carriageway through double parking (DP). In the former case, MOD vehicles must leave and rejoin the main traffic stream, potentially causing disturbances and delays; in the latter, a driving lane is (partially) obstructed, resulting in a temporary bottleneck (Vishnoi and Simoni, 2025). While empirical evidence on the impact of these processes on the overall transport system performance remains limited (Stüger et al., 2022; Hanekamp et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024), PUDOs share characteristics with other traffic disruptions such as public transport stops, delivery vehicle halts, and double parking—all of which have been shown to negatively impact network capacity and exacerbate congestion (Kladefitras and Antoniou, 2013; Cao and Menendez, 2015; Cao et al., 2016; Johari et al., 2020).

As vehicle automation advances, leading to a reduction in operational costs, the demand for Autonomous Mobility-On-Demand (AMOD) services is anticipated to grow substantially. Consequently, the movement of AMOD vehicles and their PUDO processes are likely to have a critical impact on traffic flow across significant portions of the transport network. This highlights the need for a more detailed examination of when and how PUDO processes occur, aiming to balance the interests not only of MOD users and operators, but also of the rest of the traffic participants, and society as a whole.

Existing efforts to mitigate the impacts of PUDOs and other short-term traffic stops—particularly in the context of limited curbside availability and competition with other uses (e.g., parking, charging stations, urban amenities)—have explored several strategies. These include the implementation of dynamic curbside management (Ranjbari et al., 2021) and dynamic (in-lane) parking spots (Roca-Riu et al., 2017), restrictions on PUDO activities along specific links (Stüger et al., 2022), and the introduction of static/dynamic pricing and space allocation mechanisms (Liu et al., 2023; Lim and Masoud, 2024). In addition, real-time traffic management strategies have been proposed, such as dynamically adjusting the PUDO location of individual vehicles along a roadway segment (Vishnoi and Simoni, 2025) or at intersections (Stüger et al., 2022). Overall, most existing studies considering PUDOs concentrate on operational or tactical interventions (i.e., short-term decisions such as assigning individual requests to specific stop locations based on the real-time traffic conditions, traffic signal control, and space availability), rather than exploring strategic planning measures (long-term decisions such as deciding where to provide PUDO infrastructure or enforce PUDO regulations). Besides, they typically treat the MOD fleet management as exogenous (ignoring the complex interactions between demand and supply), and their scope is often restricted to individual links or intersections, limiting their applicability to network-level analysis. Finally, many rely on computationally intensive, stochastic traffic microsimulation tools, which can constrain the scalability to larger networks.

Given this context, this study addresses the role of PUDO processes in an AMOD service with walking legs. We provide a methodology aimed at supporting city planners in making informed decisions regarding: (i) how much curbside space should be allocated to PUDO processes across the network; (ii) how this space should be distributed among different streets; and (iii) where double parking for PUDOs should be prohibited. The main contributions of the study are summarized as follows:

1. We introduce a novel, network-level, strategic planning problem: the “Congestion-Aware PUDO Network Design Problem” (CA-PUDO-NDP).
2. We develop a solution approach based on a modular framework with three components: an AMOD model incorporating PUDO location and regulation constraints, a static traffic assignment sensitive to link-level PUDO frequencies, and an upper-level optimization that employs the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (ALNS) metaheuristic to identify optimal PUDO regulation strategies.
3. We illustrate the application of the proposed solution approach in a small urban network. The proposed framework delivers quasi-optimal solutions within limited computational time, and results show how PUDO regulations, together with link characteristics (e.g., number of lanes) and demand levels, shape link-level speeds and flows.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the proposed CA-PUDO-NDP, outlining its base assumptions, and core components; Section 3 introduces the relevant literature related to the problem’s components; Section 4 presents a solution approach to the CA-PUDO-NDP, starting with an overview of the framework and then detailing the characteristics of each module; Sections 5 and 6 describe the case study used to illustrate the methodology and present its results, respectively; and Section 7 concludes the paper with a discussion of limitations and directions for future research. Appendix A summarizes the notation used across the study.

2. Problem description

The planning decision—or PUDO policy—of how many curbside spaces to be provided and whether to allow double parking PUDO in a street, corresponds to the link-level decision variables of our proposed CA-PUDO-NDP. These influence the AMOD and private vehicle routing, the number and type of PUDO processes in the links, and, ultimately, the total traffic flow. The objectives of the associated optimization problem are to minimize (O1) congestion on the streets (and thereby implicitly both the in-vehicle travel times of private vehicles and AMOD users) and (O2) walking duration of the AMOD users. Additionally, city planners will want to limit or even minimize (O3) the curbside space dedicated to PUDOs.

Let $G = (N, L)$ with nodes N and links L be a graph describing the street network of a transport system. We define decision variables $x_l \in \{0, 1\}$ and $n_l \in \mathbb{N}_0$, which describe for each link $l \in L$ whether double parking is allowed ($x_l = 1$) and how many curb spaces n_l should be dedicated to PUDOs, respectively. We denote the combination of x_l and n_l values for all links in a network as a state.

In its most general form¹, the CA-PUDO-NDP can be described as a multi-level multi-objective problem:

$$\min_{x_l, n_l} O1, O2, O3 \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } O1, O2, O3 \leftarrow TM(x_l, n_l; \dots) \quad (1b)$$

Hereby, \leftarrow symbolizes that the variables on the left are determined by the problem/model on the right side. Hereby, $TM(x_l, n_l; \dots)$ refers to a transport model (in equilibrium), which determines the objectives for a given setting of x_l and n_l . This model has to represent travel demand and supply and their interaction. There are both macroscopic and microscopic models, and they can comprise multiple interdependent sub-models, such as activity, departure time, destination, mode, and route choice. Additionally, $TM(x_l, n_l; \dots)$ needs to represent the operation of an AMOD service, including the vehicle routing.

The selection of a suitable transport model depends on the requirements. For the CA-PUDO-NDP, the transport model needs to reflect changes in the decision variables and is informative in the objectives. In other words, the travel times in the network need to be sensitive to the number and type (double parking or curbside) of PUDO processes happening in the links, and the walking durations to the available PUDO locations need to be estimated.

Importantly, it should be noted that the solution space grows exponentially with the number of links in the network, $|L|$: even if we assumed $n_l \leq n_l^{\max} = 1 \forall l \in L$, we would have a solution space with $(2 \cdot 2)^{|L|}$ possible solutions. Arguably, the CA-PUDO-NDP is a planning problem and does not have real-time requirements, but even for relatively small $|L|$, the size of the solution space requires efficient methods for both optimization and the transport model $TM(x_l, n_l; \dots)$.

Hence, we identify the key sensitivities and approximate other sub-models as constant (in the first order). For the problem at hand, the most relevant consequences of changes in x_l and n_l are assumed to be the following:

1. The AMOD service adapts its stops according to available PUDO locations. The users of the service will walk to and from the designated PUDO points if they are not their desired origin and destination.
2. The number of PUDO processes in a link l affects the traffic flow characteristics in this link, i.e., the capacity of links are reduced by vehicles blocking the lanes and the weaving processes. Moreover, the impact depends on whether the PUDOs happen in a driving lane (as double parking) or a dedicated PUDO curbside spot.
3. Vehicles will adapt their route choices based on the link travel times in the network.

Focusing on these key sensitivities, we make the following assumptions (in a first order approximation):

- (A1) A change in PUDO configuration (x_l, n_l) will not affect activities, destination choice, and mode choice, i.e., travel demand does not depend on the decision variables².
- (A2) AMOD vehicles will use curb space if it is available and stop in the traffic lane only if curb capacity is exceeded³ and double parking is allowed ($x_l = 1$).
- (A3) The AMOD provider will optimize its routes to serve a set of requests R . From the provider's perspective, there is no preference between curb and double parking.
- (A4) The AMOD vehicles follow typical routing patterns to drive between stops, i.e., are part of a user equilibrium of a traffic assignment.

Assumption (A3) means that we need to solve a vehicle routing problem (VRP) for the AMOD provider, whereas assumption (A4) requires a traffic assignment (TA) model with user equilibrium, which needs to be sensitive to PUDO processes. Due to assumption (A2), the VRP is more complex than standard VRPs. Finally, assumption (A1) enables us to use exogenous demand such that the combination of VRP and TA are sufficient.

Let R be the set of requests that the AMOD provider has to serve and D be the set of trips conducted by private vehicle. Then

$$\min_{x_l, n_l} O_1 = \sum_{p \in R \cup D} t_p^{drive}(t_l), O_2 = \sum_{r \in R} t_r^{walk}, O_3 = \sum_{l \in L} n_l \quad (2a)$$

¹ This section begins by conceptualizing the CA-PUDO-NDP and discussing it deliberately in an abstract form. It later operationalizes the different components of the problem, which is complemented by Section 4, where we introduce our proposed solution approach.

² As shown in Farahani et al. (2013), most network design problems consider inelastic demand.

³ Same assumption was made in Alho et al. (2018).

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{s.t. } & (n_{od}^{AMOD}, f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}, t_r^{walk}) \leftarrow \text{VRP}(x_l, n_l; t_l; R) & (2b) \\
& t_l \leftarrow \text{TA}(n_{od}^{AMOD}, n_{od}^{PV}, f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}) & (2c) \\
& 0 \leq n_l \leq n_l^{max} & \forall l \in L & (2d) \\
& n_l \in \mathbb{N}_0 & \forall l \in L & (2e) \\
& x_l \in \{0, 1\} & \forall l \in L & (2f)
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. (2a) gives expressions for the three objectives. O_1 is computed by summing up all the in-vehicle travel times of all AMOD and private vehicle (PV) passengers. O_2 collects all the walking times of AMOD users. Finally, O_3 aims at minimizing the space that has to be dedicated to AMOD processes in the whole network, also denoted by $N_{city} = \sum_{l \in L} n_l$. Eqs. (2b) and (2c) describe the transport system. A VRP with walking legs considering travel times t_l and PUDO constraints is solved to find the stop sequence and the PUDOs (including walking legs) of AMOD vehicles. From these sequences, the AMOD trips, n_{od}^{AMOD} , as well as the number of PUDOs per link can be determined. These can be split according to assumption (A2) into frequencies for both curbside (f_l^{curb}) and double parking (f_l^{dbl}) PUDOs. Finally, a TA sensitive to these PUDO frequencies assigns both AMOD and private vehicle demands ($n_{od}^{AMOD}, n_{od}^{PV}$) to find the user equilibrium in order to determine the link travel times in the network, t_l , and thereby also the in-vehicle travel times t_p of all travelers $p \in R \cup D$. Finally, Eqs. (2d)–(2f) describe the domains of the binary (x_l) and non-negative integer (n_l) decision variables, where n_l^{max} represents the physical limit of curbside spots that can be dedicated for PUDOs in link l .

Because of the circular dependency between the VRP (depending on t_l and determining $n_{od}^{AMOD}, f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}$) and the TA (depending on $n_{od}^{AMOD}, f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}$ and affecting t_l), Eqs. (2b) and (2c) represent an equilibrium problem. Attributes of this equilibrium problem will depend significantly on the exact formulations (and solution approaches) of the VRP and the TA. We expect an iterative fixed-point algorithm to find an (approximate) equilibrium.

We define a request $r \in R$ by a tuple (τ_r, o_r, d_r) with $o_r, d_r \in L$, together with time windows $[\tau_r^{o,early}, \tau_r^{o,late}]$ and $[\tau_r^{d,early}, \tau_r^{d,late}]$ at the origin and destination, respectively. We set an evaluation period such that all times $\tau \in T = [0, T^{max}]$. The choice of request time τ_r determines whether the VRP is static ($\tau_r = 0 \forall r \in R$) or dynamic. For the formulation of the VRP, we follow the three-index notation (Savelsbergh and Sol, 1995) $x_{\rho\mu}^v$, with $v \in V$ representing the vehicles, and $\rho, \mu \in S$ representing stops to pick up (s_r^p) and drop off (s_r^d) users, where $S = \{1 \dots s_r^p \dots |R|, |R| + 1 \dots s_r^d \dots |2R|\}$. Moreover, we define the two subsets $S^p = \{1 \dots s_r^p \dots |R|\}$ and $S^d = \{|R| + 1 \dots s_r^d \dots |2R|\}$ as the pick-up and drop-off stops, respectively, as well as the set of stops including the depot $S^0 = S \cup \{0\}$. We denote the occupancy change at stop ρ by ΔQ_ρ , which is +1 in case of a pick-up and -1 for a drop-off. The capacity of vehicles is denoted by Q and the occupancy of vehicle v after stop ρ by Q_ρ^v .

Changes to standard VRPs are necessary due to walking legs and PUDO capacity constraints. δ_ρ^l is a binary decision variable taking the value of 1 if stop $\rho \in S$ is conducted at link $l \in L$. Hence, $\delta_{s_r^p}^{o_r} = 0$ or $\delta_{s_r^d}^{d_r} = 0$ signalize a pick-up or drop-off with walking leg. B_l denotes the PUDO start time at link $l \in L$, and we assume a constant stop time for boarding of t^b . ω_ρ^l is a binary variable that is 1 during the boarding time of stop ρ . The network travel times and distances between two links $i, j \in L$ are given by t_{ij} and d_{ij} , respectively. Finally, $N_l = N_l(n_l, x_l)$ determines the PUDO capacity, which we define as the maximum number of concurrent PUDO processes on link l .

We use the following assumption to determine the value of N_l :

(A5) PUDOs can occur on a link either at the curbside or via double parking, with both options requiring a similar amount of longitudinal space, L^{car} . PUDO processes are not allowed at intersections (i.e., nodes) to avoid interfering with all inbound and outbound links. AMOD vehicles must be able to access their assigned PUDO location without being obstructed by other dwelling vehicles; therefore, double parking is not permitted alongside an active curbside bay. Furthermore, to prevent blocking the upstream and downstream intersections and their pedestrian crossings, in a protected section of the link, L^{prot} , PUDOs are not allowed. As expressed in Eq. (3), when $x_l = 1$, the value of N_l does not depend on the number of assigned curbside bays n_l , but rather on L^{car} , L^{prot} , and the total link length L_l .

$$N_l = \begin{cases} n_l & \text{if } x_l = 0 \\ \lfloor (L_l - L^{prot}) / L^{car} \rfloor & \text{if } x_l = 1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

We want to highlight that due to assumptions (A3) and (A5), the VRP is independent of n_l as long as $x_l = 1$. In practice, Assumption (A5) may not hold, as curbside and in-lane PUDOs likely interact, making N_l depend on the number of curbside bays, n_l . For example, curbside and double-parking activities can interfere—especially on one-lane links—reducing the effective PUDO length. Conversely, on high-demand streets, double-parking alongside curbside PUDOs may increase it. While these effects could be modeled by defining N_l for $x_l = 1$ as a function of the available length, $(L_l - L^{prot})$, and the number of curbside bays, n_l , we lack empirical data to parameterize such a relationship. Given this and the paper's scope, we do not include these interactions in the current framework.

The objectives of the AMOD provider can be multifold. Here, we mention the fleet size $|V|$, the operating costs (with c_{ij} being the costs to drive between network links $i, j \in L$), and the walking costs for users, but we could extend it, e.g., for the earliest arrival time of requests at their destination.

$$\min_{x, \delta, B, \omega} |V| \cdot \sum_{v \in V} \sum_{i, j \in L^2} \sum_{\rho, \mu \in S^2} c_{ij} \delta_\rho^i \delta_\mu^j x_{\rho\mu}^v \cdot \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{l \in L} \left(d_{o_r, l} \delta_{s_r^p}^{o_r} + d_{d_r, l} \delta_{s_r^d}^{d_r} \right) \quad (4a)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{s.t. } \sum_{v \in V} \sum_{\rho \in S^0} x_{\rho\mu}^v &= 1 & \forall \mu \in S & \quad (4b) \\
 \sum_{\rho \in S^0} x_{\rho\mu}^v &= \sum_{\rho \in S^0} x_{\mu\rho}^v & \forall \mu \in S, \forall v \in V & \quad (4c) \\
 \sum_{\rho \in S^0} x_{s_r^p, \rho} &= \sum_{\rho \in S^0} x_{s_r^d, \rho} & \forall r \in R, \forall v \in V & \quad (4d) \\
 Q_\rho^v + \Delta Q_\mu &\leq Q + (1 - x_{\rho\mu}^v) \cdot M & \forall \rho, \mu \in S, \forall v \in V & \quad (4e) \\
 \sum_{j \in L} \delta_{s_r^d}^j B_j^v - \left(\sum_{i \in L} \delta_{s_r^p}^i (B_i^v + t^b + t_{ij}) \right) &\geq 0 & \forall r \in R, \forall v \in V & \quad (4f) \\
 \tau_r^{o,early} &\leq \sum_{l \in L} \delta_{s_r^p}^l (B_l^v - v^{walk} \cdot d_{o,l}) \leq \tau_r^{o,late} & \forall \rho \in S^P, \forall v \in V & \quad (4g) \\
 \tau_r^{d,early} &\leq \sum_{l \in L} \delta_{s_r^d}^l (B_l^v + v^{walk} \cdot d_{l,d_r}) \leq \tau_r^{d,late} & \forall \rho \in S^D, \forall v \in V & \quad (4h) \\
 \sum_{l \in L} \delta_{s_r^o}^l &= 1 & \forall r \in R & \quad (4i) \\
 \sum_{l \in L} \delta_{s_r^d}^l &= 1 & \forall r \in R & \quad (4j) \\
 \omega_\rho^t &= \theta \left(t - \sum_{v \in V} \sum_{j \in L} \delta_\rho^j B_j^v \right) - \theta \left(\sum_{v \in V} \sum_{j \in L} \delta_\rho^j B_j^v + t^b - t \right) & \forall \rho \in S & \quad (4k) \\
 \sum_{\rho \in S} \delta_\rho^l \omega_\rho^t &\leq N_l & \forall t \in T & \quad (4l) \\
 x_{\rho\mu}^v &\in \{0, 1\} & \forall \rho, \mu \in S^0, \forall v \in V & \quad (4m) \\
 \delta_\rho^l &\in \{0, 1\} & \forall \rho \in S, \forall l \in L & \quad (4n) \\
 B_l^v &\in T & \forall l \in L, v \in V & \quad (4o) \\
 \omega_\rho^t &\in \{0, 1\} & \forall \rho \in S, \forall t \in T & \quad (4p)
 \end{aligned}$$

Eqs. (4b) to (4e) are in the standard form for VRPs. Eq. (4b) guarantees service for each request, Eq. (4c) ensures vehicle flow conservation, Eq. (4d) prohibits one request from being served by multiple vehicles, and Eq. (4e) limits the passengers on a vehicle. Hereby, M is a large number, which guarantees the feasibility of the equation in case $x_{\rho\mu}^v = 0$. Eqs. (4f) to (4j) are adapted from standard VRPs due to the introduction of walking legs. Eq. (4f) determines the precedence; it relates the start of a stop with the start of the prior stop at given network links $i, j \in L$, which at least have to be separated in time by the duration of a boarding process t^b and the fastest path travel time between the two network links t_{ij} . Eqs. (4g) and (4h) connect the stop times at the PUDO locations with the time windows at a request’s origin and destination location, respectively. Hence, the walking duration is added to the constraints at the origin location, or equivalently, subtracted at the pick-up stop. Similarly, the walking duration is added to the drop-off stop. Eqs. (4i) and (4j) are constraints ensuring that exactly one link is selected for pick-up and drop-off. Eqs. (4k) and (4l) model the PUDO capacity condition. Hereby, $\theta(x)$ is the heavyside function, letting ω_ρ^t indicate the times $t \in T$, at which stop $\rho \in S$ is performed. Eq. (4l) limits the number of concurrent PUDOs at links to N_l , which was defined in Eq. (3). Finally, Eqs. (4m) to (4p) define the domain of the decision variables.

Compared to standard VRPs, the addition of walking legs makes the problem more complex, but they do not alter the general structure. In contrast, the introduction of the PUDO capacity constraint introduces a continuous temporal interrelation between all stops, thereby increasing the complexity of the NP-hard VRP even further.

After solving the VRP, we can compute the PUDO frequencies and the number of trips between all OD-pairs on link-level.

$$f_l^{curb} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^{T^{max}} \min \left(n_l, \sum_{\rho \in S} \delta_\rho^l \omega_\rho^t \right) dt \quad \forall l \in L \quad (5a)$$

$$f_l^{dbl} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^{T^{max}} \max \left(0, \sum_{\rho \in S} \delta_\rho^l \omega_\rho^t - n_l \right) dt \quad \forall l \in L \quad (5b)$$

$$\hat{n}_{od}^{AMOD} = \sum_{v \in V} \sum_{\rho \in S} \sum_{\mu \in S} x_{\rho\mu}^v \delta_\rho^o \delta_\mu^d \quad \forall o, d \in L \quad (5c)$$

Typical TA algorithms assume node-based demand. Hence, we transform the link-based AMOD OD-demand \hat{n}_{od}^{AMOD} to a node-based version n_{od}^{AMOD} with the following assumption:

(A6) For a given link-level OD, let $o, d \in L$ denote the (directed) street network links connecting nodes $n_o^o, n_d^o \in N$ and $n_o^d, n_d^d \in N$, respectively. Then, the AMOD trips are assumed part of the general vehicle flow between the nodes n_o^o and n_o^d , i.e. the end node of the starting link and the start node of the ending link. The impact on traffic flow in the PUDO links is modeled via the modification in the link-performance functions $t_l = t_l(q; f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl})$ for $l \in \{o, d\}$.

For a given trip demand containing both private and AMOD vehicles, a TA can determine the link flows and travel times in the user equilibrium for the network.

$$\min_{q, f} \sum_{l \in L} \int_0^{q_l} t_l(\bar{q}; f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}) d\bar{q} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{p \in P_{od}} f_p = (n_{od}^{PV} + n_{od}^{AMOD}) \quad \forall o, d \in N \quad (6b)$$

$$q_l = \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{l \in L} \Omega_l^p f_p \quad \forall l \in L \quad (6c)$$

$$f_p \geq 0 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (6d)$$

$$q_l \geq 0 \quad \forall l \in L \quad (6e)$$

Hereby, the objective (6a) is a mathematical construct that helps to represent the user equilibrium (Sheffi, 1985), in which no single user gains something from changing their route. Eq. (6b) relates the path flows with the OD-demands, Eq. (6c) connects the path and link flows, and Eqs. (6d) and (6e) define the domains of the decision variables. The difference to standard TA problems is the link-performance function $t_l(\bar{q}; f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl})$, which can be pre-processed after the VRP is solved.

As mentioned before, the combination of VRP (with walking legs) and TA represents a novel equilibrium problem, but its analysis is outside the scope of this paper. Hence, we make another simplifying assumption.

(A7) The sequence of stops (and thereby the determination of deadheading, solo and pooled trips) of AMOD vehicles is based on an expected traffic state with expected travel times t_l^{exp} , which we assume to be independent of the PUDO configuration.

This assumption enables us to break the circular dependency of the VRP and the TA. The CA-PUDO-NDP shown in Eq. (2) breaks down into three components, namely the determination of stop sequences of an AMOD fleet with a VRP (Eq. (4) with t_l replaced by t_l^{exp}), the assignment of trips onto the network in the TA with modified link-performance functions (Eq. (6)), and the optimization of the decision variables (x_j, n_j) in a very high-dimensional solution space. In B, we present the results of a numerical experiment comparing the objective values obtained when enforcing Assumption (A7) against those derived from an iterative fixed-point VRP \leftrightarrow TA equilibrium. The results indicate that the objective values differ only minimally across several thousand scenarios spanning different AMOD shares and network-wide curbside supply levels, thereby supporting the validity of Assumption (A7).

3. State of the art

We structure this literature section according to these three components of our CA-PUDO-NDP, starting with AMOD modeling, then coming to the traffic assignment, and concluding with the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search metaheuristic.

3.1. AMOD modeling

Demand-responsive transport, especially the underlying vehicle routing problems, is already addressed by research since decades (Psaraftis et al., 2016). This class of mathematical problems investigates how a set of vehicles can be routed through a network, to pick-up and drop-off a set of requests given time and capacity constraints in an optimal way with respect to various objective functions.

Mathematical models were developed to create more general (mostly managerial) insights. To be analytically tractable, they are usually of macroscopic nature. Herminghaus (2019) and Ng et al. (2025) provide models describing the service performance indicators for plane operating areas. Some models (e.g., Ke et al., 2020a; Zhang and Nie, 2021) focus on the market equilibrium and do not look at traffic impacts. To account for these, Ke et al. (2020b) and Bilali et al. (2022) model the vehicle accumulation and trip generation in Macroscopic Fundamental Diagrams (MFDs). While having many applications, these spatially and temporally aggregated models do not represent the street network on the link level and cannot be sensitive to single trips and their PUDO processes on specific links, which is required for the CA-PUDO-NDP.

On the opposite end of spatial and temporal resolution, there is a significant amount of research on the fleet operational tasks (Hyland and Mahmassani, 2017; Molenbruch et al., 2017; Mourad et al., 2019). The operators require efficient algorithms for the dynamic VRP, in which single user requests become known to the operators as time evolves. Service designs can vary in the constraints and objectives; whether pooling is allowed or only solo rides are permitted, and the maximum acceptable waiting time, are two constraints that significantly limit the solution space (Alonso-Mora et al., 2017). Contrary, asking users to walk to or from PUDO locations increases the solution space as each request can be assigned to several possible locations. Stiglic et al. (2015) predefine a set of meeting points, and use K-d trees to find a small set of nearby meeting points, for which they create matches between drivers and riders. Similarly, Engelhardt and Bogenberger (2021) and Fielbaum et al. (2021) create hypothetical requests for each origin-destination pair of nearby access points for dynamic assignment, develop heuristics to keep the problem tractable, and show that even with walking as slow access and egress mode, this can lead to a win-win situation for the fleet provider (more requests served with higher pooling efficiency) and the users (more requests served at similar journey time). Research is still ongoing as the dynamic and stochastic nature of the problem often prohibits (temporally and spatially) global optimal solutions in reasonable computation time. To evaluate the algorithms in this dynamic and stochastic context, agent-based simulations tracking the evolution of states and available information are necessary.

For planning problems like the CA-PUDO-NDP, it is (often) not desirable to run this time-intensive stochastic simulations, but rather look at the static problem. However, the static problem has more variables and a much larger solution space. Hence, heuristic approaches have been developed, especially for pooled-ride service (Kucharski and Cats, 2020) and pooled-ride services with walking legs (Kucharski and Cats, 2024; Fielbaum and Alonso-Mora, 2024).

3.2. Traffic assignment

The CA-PUDO-NDP addresses strategic transport planning as it optimizes the positioning of stop areas for AMODs in the network. In the transport literature, these kinds of problems are summarized under the term “network design problem” (NDP) that typically differentiates between transit network design and road network design problems. The CA-PUDO-NDP is part of the latter. NDPs can be further distinguished by addressing the network topology or the parameterization of the network (Bell and Lida, 1997). Typical decision variables in NDPs for road network design questions are link position, lane configuration, link capacity, turning restrictions, road user tolls, etc. Farahani et al. (2013); in other words, identifying the optimal location of facilities that shall be added to the transport network (Friesz, 1985). In all these problems, the lower-level optimization problem is concerned with distributing trips in the network. Here, the literature presents two main approaches depending on whether congestion effects should be considered or not. In case congestion effects are not considered, the assignment becomes an “all-or-nothing” (AON) assignment, while in case congestion is considered, Wardrop’s 1952 “user equilibrium” (UE) traffic assignment with a static model is chosen. It is noted frequently that the lower level is traditionally a user equilibrium (e.g., Yang and Bell G., 1998; Wang et al., 2013); for example, Behbahani et al. (2019) and Loder et al. (2022). Extensions to the stochastic user equilibrium, and with elastic demand are also possible (Yang and Bell G., 1998). Also, in strategic transport planning, the user equilibrium principle with a static model is the most widely used (Bliemer et al., 2016).

The user equilibrium can be formulated as a convex optimization problem (Beckmann et al., 1956) or a variational inequality (Nagurney, 1993). Three types of algorithms to solve the traffic assignment problems have been developed. First, link-based algorithms model link flows, not path flows, and thus require less computational resources, but they are slow in terms of convergence. Common algorithms here are the Method of Successive Average, Frank-Wolfe, or Conjugate Frank-Wolfe. Second, path-based algorithms model path flows, i.e., they can compute link flows, are richer in terms of information, and tend to converge faster, but require more computational resources. Third, bush-based algorithms are considered the most recent development and aim at having path-based computation speeds at less computational resources, but they are more complex and require more implementation skills (Boyles et al., 2025). As in NDPs the traffic assignment is frequently executed, using algorithms like Frank-Wolfe is inefficient (Bell and Lida, 1997).

3.3. Adaptive large neighborhood search

In the proposed CA-PUDO-NDP, the objective function relies on the outputs of a transport model—comprising a VRP and a TA—rather than a closed-form expression. This characteristic rules out the application of gradient-based or exact integer optimization methods, thereby motivating the use of approximate algorithms such as heuristics and metaheuristics. The latter are high-level strategies that guide the heuristic search toward high-quality solutions for computationally hard problems (Blum and Roli, 2003).

Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (ALNS) is one such metaheuristic. It builds on the concept of Large Neighborhood Search (Shaw, 1997), in which a solution/state is iteratively “destroyed” and “repaired” using a set of predefined methods (operators). The ALNS framework proposed in Ropke and Pisinger (2006) and Pisinger and Ropke (2010) extends this approach by enabling the use of multiple *neighborhoods* within the same search process in an adaptive manner. More specifically, the weights governing the selection of destroy and repair operators—initially all equal—are updated after each iteration to reflect their relative performance. The combination of the selected destroy and repair methods defines the neighborhood explored in that iteration.

A key strength of ALNS, compared to other local search algorithms, is that it does not require the researcher to ensure the effectiveness of each operator; the algorithm naturally reduces the use of ineffective ones (Pisinger and Ropke, 2007). Furthermore, ALNS provides the flexibility to incorporate domain-specific operators tailored to the problem context. These characteristics make ALNS particularly well-suited for complex problems such as the CA-PUDO-NDP, where solution evaluation is computationally expensive and the search space is large and presumably contains numerous local minima.

ALNS has been widely applied in transport and logistics (Windras Mara et al., 2022), particularly for problems involving routing, scheduling, vehicle capacity, personnel planning, and network design. Its applications span multiple transport modes, including rail (Barrena et al., 2014; Canca et al., 2017), bus (Galarza Montenegro et al., 2021), shipping (Bakkehaug et al., 2016), and aviation (Martins de Sá et al., 2015). In the logistics context, ALNS has been used for multimodal hub location and planning (Real et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2025) and in the shared-mobility context, for ride-sharing matching (Guo et al., 2025) and bike-sharing repositioning (Ho and Szeto, 2017), among others. However, all applications above differ substantially from the nature of the problem addressed in this study, underscoring the novelty of our approach.

4. Methodology

After having introduced the general form of the CA-PUDO-NDP in Section 2, we now present a solution approach based on a modular framework with three components: an AMOD model incorporating PUDO location and regulation constraints, a static traffic assignment sensitive to link-level PUDO frequencies, and an upper-level optimization that employs a metaheuristic to identify optimal

PUDO regulation strategies. The following sections provide an overview of the framework, followed by a deep dive into each of the modules, their features, and key assumptions.

4.1. Overall framework

Considering the objectives and decision variables of our framework, presented in Section 2, the optimization problem can be categorized as an integer, non-linear, multi-objective optimization problem. Additionally, the objectives cannot be evaluated easily but require simulation-based methods.

Moreover, for a given demand and combination of (x_l, n_l) , we note that it cannot be guaranteed that the PUDO infrastructure is sufficient to handle all PUDO processes simultaneously. Hence, we transform the hard constraint in Eq. (41) into a soft constraint by defining a PUDO capacity exceedance ($PUDO_{exceedance}^{cap}$):

$$O4 = PUDO_{exceedance}^{cap} = \sum_{l \in L} \int_0^{T^{max}} \max \left(0, \sum_{\rho \in S} \delta_\rho^l \omega_\rho^t - N_l \right) dt \quad (7)$$

which is added as a primary objective (with large penalty factor M) to the upper-level optimization.

Given the challenge of simultaneously considering conflicting objectives of such a diverse nature, we propose to aggregate the driving times ($O1$) and walking times ($O2$) objectives into a single (composite) objective, as shown in the objective function (8a), which includes weights that represent the relative valuation of in-vehicle and walking times (VOT^{drive} and VOT^{walk}), respectively.

$$\min_{x_l, n_l} O(x_l, n_l) = \left[\sum_{r=1}^R t_r^{drive}(t_l) + \sum_{d=1}^D t_d^{drive}(t_l) \right] VOT^{drive} + \left[\sum_{r=1}^R t_r^{walk} \right] VOT^{walk} + M \cdot O4 \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \left(n_{od}^{AMOD}, f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}, t_r^{walk}, \delta_\rho^l, \omega_\rho^t \right) \leftarrow \text{VRP}(x_l, n_l; t_l^{exp}; R) \quad (8b)$$

$$t_l \leftarrow \text{TA}(n_{od}^{AMOD}, n_{od}^{PV}, f_l^{curb}, f_l^{dbl}) \quad (8c)$$

$$\sum_{l \in L} n_l = N_{city} \quad (8d)$$

$$0 \leq n_l \leq n_l^{max} \quad \forall l \in L \quad (8e)$$

$$n_l \in \mathbb{N}_0 \quad \forall l \in L \quad (8f)$$

$$x_l \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l \in L \quad (8g)$$

Conversely, we propose to account for the objective of minimizing the curbside space dedicated to PUDOs ($O3$) by including it as a scenario variable, represented by constraint (8d). Additionally, constraints (8e) and (8f) define n_l as integer, lower or equal than the maximum physical number of curbside stop areas in each link, n_l^{max} . We chose not to include ($O3$) in the objective function (8a), as reliable monetary estimates for the value of curbside space are difficult to obtain. Moreover, this objective differs in nature from the other two, as it represents an externality of the transport system. Instead, through the exploration of different values of N_{city} , it will be possible to approximate the value from which the marginal improvement in the objective function is irrelevant. Alternatively, policymakers can assess how pursuing a given “social” ($O3$) objective impacts the objective of transport system participants.

The above problem has two relevant characteristics. First, the objective function does not have a closed mathematical form, but it depends on the computationally expensive evaluation of the AMOD and Traffic Assignment modules, which are described in more detail in Sections 4.2 and 4.3, respectively. Second, the solution space, S , is very large, since, $|S| = \prod_{l=1}^L 2(n_l^{max} + 1)$ and L can be large for real networks. Therefore, exploring exhaustively the whole space through brute force is computationally not feasible. To face these challenges, we propose adapting the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (ALNS) metaheuristic (Ropke and Pisinger, 2006) to the context of our problem. In particular, we adapt the notion of *neighborhood* of a solution, and develop tailored destroy and repair methods, as further described in Section 4.4.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the ALNS metaheuristic is built around the two other modules of the CA-PUDO-NDP. In the following, we provide a high-level overview of the framework, but the specifics of each of the elements and modules are presented in the respective sections of the methodology. To guide readers through the flowchart, we map its key components with the explanation in the next paragraph using numbers in blue.

Given a network (its topology and n_l^{max} values), the iterative process for a certain *problem*—defined by a given N_{city} constraint, the AMOD and Private Vehicle (PV) demands—takes the following steps. First [1], at the initialization of the process, the AMOD and PV demand are combined into a total trip demand, and given to an (initial) traffic assignment, which calculates the expected link travel times (t_l^{exp}), used by the AMOD module during the whole optimization process⁴.

Then [2], from the solution space of the problem—determined by the network—an initial *feasible* solution is sampled, i.e., one that satisfies constraints (8d) to (8g). In particular, the allocation of up to n_l^{max} curbside spaces to every link, in (8e), is referred to as the link-level constraint, while the allocation of a total of N_{city} spaces in the whole network, in (8d), is referred to as the network-level constraint. Next [3], at iteration 0, the objective value of this initial feasible solution is calculated—for the sake of clarity, we provide more details later on—and this initial solution is destroyed by one of the implemented destroy methods (described in Section 4.4.2).

⁴ Following assumption (A5), described in Section 2.

Fig. 1. Overview of our proposed solution approach of the CA-PUDO-NDP based on the ALNS metaheuristic. Solid arrows describe process flow and dashed ones information flow. [Numbers] match the steps in the description.

The destroyed solution is then given to one of the repair methods [4] (described in Section 4.4.3). Each of these identifies the neighborhood of the destroyed solution following a different approach. In most cases, the neighborhood contains a large number of elements, making the exhaustive exploration of the neighborhood impossible⁵. For this reason, depending on the available computation resources (e.g., the number of CPUs), a number C of candidate neighbors are sampled from the neighborhood, and their objective function is evaluated concurrently. The evaluation of the objective function (also for the above-described initial feasible solution) consists of solving the VRP problem by the AMOD module, calculating the value of $PUDO_{exceedance}^{cap}$, updating the link performance function of each link based on their PUDO frequencies (in the curbside and as double parking), and conducting the static traffic assignment. Then, given the study-specific VOT^{drive} and VOT^{walk} , the objective value for each candidate solution is obtained, and the best candidate is chosen as repaired solution.

Finally [5], following the standard ALNS approach, depending on the implemented acceptance criterion, either the repaired solution, s_{it}^c , or the best already-visited solution, s^* , will be given to the destroy method for the next iteration (see Section 4.4.4). This iterative process will continue until a pre-defined stop condition is met (e.g., maximum number of iterations or running time, or the best solution has not been improved after a number of iterations).

4.2. AMOD module

This section describes our solution approach to the VRP from Eq. (4). Additional to the tasks posed by standard VRPs, we have the following challenges:

1. unknown fleet size
2. PUDOs are not necessarily at request locations
3. PUDOs need to be coordinated to stay within PUDO capacities

⁵ By contrast, in classic ALNS applications such as vehicle routing, evaluating a single solution typically involves a direct combinatorial cost calculation with very low computational effort, making it feasible to exhaustively explore the neighborhood.

Since the CA-PUDO-NDP is a planning problem, we can look at the static version of the problem, i.e., $\tau_r = 0 \forall r \in R$. Given the overall scope of the upper-level optimization, we look for a computationally-efficient heuristic approach. Hence, we divide the overall problem into several easier to solve sub-problems.

Our strategy is as follows. First, we simplify the vehicle routing problem into a trip finding problem for the requests and select a subset of these trips such that all requests are served—similar to [Santi et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Kucharski and Cats \(2020\)](#). In this step, we can include the search for different PUDOs on the trip level. For this study, we assume vehicle capacity $Q = 1$, as this reflects the predominant ride-hailing mode in current MOD services, and severely limits the solution space and speeds up computation. Next, we discretize time to check the PUDO capacity constraints and compute $PUDO_{exceedance}^{cap}$ for the selected trips. Finally, we develop a method that puts vehicle routes through the selected trips with the primary objective of minimal fleet size.

4.2.1. Trip generation and selection

Whereas this is the most expensive step for ride-pooling, for the hailing case this step is rather simple. With the assumptions that $VOT^{walk} \cdot v^{walk} < VOT^{drive} \cdot \min(L_l/t_l^{exp})$, the AMOD provider will only include walking legs for request r if PUDOs are forbidden in the respective link, i.e.,

$$x_{o_r} + n_{o_r} = 0 \quad \vee \quad x_{d_r} + n_{d_r} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Hence, we have four cases:

- (a) $n_l + x_l > 0$ for $l = \{o_r, d_r\}$: in this case, nothing needs to be done
- (b) $n_{o_r} + x_{o_r} = 0$ and $n_{d_r} + x_{d_r} > 0$
- (c) $n_{o_r} + x_{o_r} > 0$ and $n_{d_r} + x_{d_r} = 0$
- (d) $n_{o_r} + x_{o_r} = 0$ and $n_{d_r} + x_{d_r} = 0$

In case (b), we need to solve the optimization problem

$$\min_{\hat{o}_r \in L} J(\hat{o}_r) = VOT^{walk} \cdot v^{walk} \cdot d_{o_r, \hat{o}_r} + VOT^{drive} \cdot t_{\hat{o}_r, d_r}^{exp} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, case (c) leads to the optimization problem

$$\min_{\hat{d}_r \in L} J(\hat{d}_r) = VOT^{walk} \cdot v^{walk} \cdot d_{\hat{d}_r, d_r} + VOT^{drive} \cdot t_{o_r, \hat{d}_r}^{exp} \quad (11)$$

Both problems can be solved exactly by a dynamic programming approach following Dijkstra's algorithm. Starting from o_r (d_r), the connected links in both directions are explored using a priority queue with the distance to o_r (d_r) as cost. If a link l with $n_l + x_l > 0$ is found, the objective is evaluated and compared to the best solution. The algorithm can be terminated when the walking component of the objective is larger than the current best solution or the destination is reached.

A bi-directional search algorithm will be used in case (d) to solve the optimization problem

$$\min_{\hat{o}_r, \hat{d}_r \in L} J(\hat{o}_r, \hat{d}_r) = VOT^{walk} \cdot v^{walk} \cdot (d_{o_r, \hat{o}_r} + d_{\hat{d}_r, d_r}) + VOT^{drive} \cdot v^{drive} \cdot t_{\hat{o}_r, \hat{d}_r}^{exp} \quad (12)$$

The algorithm will search connected links in both directions from both origin and destination. It will do so in turns; whenever a new link l with $n_l + x_l > 0$ is found around the origin (destination), the objective $J(\hat{o}_r, \hat{d}_r)$ is evaluated for all candidate destinations (origins). The algorithm can be terminated when the sum of walking components of the objective is larger than the current best solution or either search reaches the source of the other.

For both the PUDO capacity constraint and the vehicle routing in [Section 4.2.3](#), we need to compute stop times B_l (independent of v) for all cases. For simplicity, we make the assumption that trips are pre-booked and do not have any time flexibility, i.e., $\tau_r^o = \tau_r^{o,early} = \tau_r^{o,late}$ and $\tau_r^d = \tau_r^{d,early} = \tau_r^{d,late}$. Hence, $B_o = \tau_r^o$ in cases (a) and (c), and $B_{\hat{o}} = \tau_r^o + v^{walk} \cdot d_{o_r, \hat{o}_r}$ in cases (b) and (d). The stop time at the destination can be computed by adding the correct fastest route travel time between the respective pick-up (o or \hat{o}) and drop-off (d or \hat{d}) locations.

After all trips are generated, we can select trips such that each request will be served by exactly one trip. Let Ξ^{all} be the set of all generated trips, Ξ_r all trips containing request $r \in R$, and c_ξ the cost of trip ξ . Then we solve the following set cover problem:

$$\min_{y_\xi} C_R(x_\xi) = \sum_{\xi \in \Xi^{all}} c_\xi \cdot y_\xi \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{\xi \in \Xi_r} y_\xi = 1 \quad \forall r \in R \quad (13b)$$

$$y_\xi \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall \xi \in \Xi^{all} \quad (13c)$$

where y_ξ is a binary decision variable indicating whether trip ξ is selected ($y_\xi = 1$) or not ($y_\xi = 0$).

Several comments are in place here. First, even though we are only looking at the ride-hailing case here, the methodologies introduced by [Fielbaum et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Kucharski and Cats \(2024\)](#) could be used at this stage (with minor modifications) to include the ride-pooling trips as well before solving the set cover problem in [Eq. \(13\)](#). Second, we only have a single trip for each request at this stage and, therefore, the trip selection is trivial and we do not have to specify a cost/utility function c_ξ for trips $\xi \in \Xi$.

4.2.2. PUDO capacity constraint

Let Ξ be the set of selected trips. Each trip ξ can be characterized by a sequence of stops $\rho \in S_\xi$, their PUDO location link l given by δ_ρ^l , and their start time of the boarding by $B_{l\rho} = \delta_\rho^l \cdot B_l$. Moreover, let $S_\Xi = \cup_{\xi \in \Xi} S_\xi$ be the set of all stops of all selected trips. Our approach is to discretize the PUDO times (41), capacity (hard) constraints (41), and PUDO capacity exceedance $PUDO_{cap}^{exceedance}$ (7) by introducing time bins of size t^b . Let $\Gamma = \{0, 1, \dots, \lfloor T^{\max}/t^b \rfloor\}$ be the set of time steps. Then, we can rewrite the equations in the VRP (4) as

$$\omega_\rho^\gamma = \begin{cases} 1 & \gamma = \sum_{l \in L} \delta_\rho^l \lfloor B_l/t^b \rfloor \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \forall \rho \in S_\xi \quad (14a)$$

$$\sum_{\rho \in S_\Xi} \delta_\rho^l \omega_\rho^\gamma \leq N_l \quad \forall l \in L, \forall \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (14b)$$

and the soft constraint as

$$O4 = \sum_{l \in L} \sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \max \left(0, \sum_{\rho \in S} \delta_\rho^l \omega_\rho^\gamma - N_l \right) \quad (15)$$

In this study, we approach the problem from a city planner's perspective, aiming to guarantee that the capacity of PUDOs is sufficient to meet the demand on any link where PUDOs are permitted. Alternatively, one could adopt AMOD operational algorithms to adjust trips in case of violations. For instance, if condition (14b) is violated for link l in time bin γ , walking legs could be added to redirect travelers to a stop ρ with $\omega_\rho^\gamma = 1 \wedge \delta_\rho^l = 1$. Since there are many possible approaches to make these modifications, and they fall outside the scope of strategic planning, we leave this (AMOD-operational) topic for future research.

4.2.3. Fleet size determination and vehicle routing

The input to this part of the algorithm is the set Ξ of selected (and possibly corrected) trips. The goal is to connect the selected trips with empty vehicle trips such that the number of required vehicles and the empty trip distances are minimized, where the vehicle minimization is the prioritized objective. Hence, only the first and last stops of a trip are relevant.

We create a sink/depot 0 with infinitely available vehicles and create decision variables $z_{0\xi}$ for each trip $\xi \in \Xi$, representing the case that a new vehicle will be required for a specific trip, and define $\Xi^0 = \Xi \cup \{0\}$. Additionally, we create binary decision variables $z_{\xi\phi}$ for all $\xi \in \Xi^0, \phi \in \Xi$ with the following costs:

$$c_{\xi\phi} = \begin{cases} M & \xi = 0 \\ d_{l_1, l_2} & B_{l_1\rho} + t_{l_1, l_2}^{exp} + t^b \leq B_{l_2\mu} \\ M^2 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where ρ is the last stop of ξ at link l_1 and μ is the first stop of ϕ at link l_2 , and $M \gg \max(d_{l_1, l_2})$ a very large constant value that leads to the minimization of fleet size $|V|$ and the avoidance of infeasible solutions.

Then we can find the fleet size and the vehicle routes by solving another set cover problem:

$$\min_z \sum_{\xi \in \Xi^0, \phi \in \Xi} c_{\xi\phi} \cdot z_{\xi\phi} \quad (17a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{\xi \in \Xi^0} z_{\xi\phi} = 1 \quad \forall \phi \in \Xi \quad (17b)$$

$$\sum_{\phi \in \Xi} z_{\xi\phi} = 1 \quad \forall \xi \in \Xi \quad (17c)$$

$$z_{\xi\phi} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall \xi \in \Xi^0, \forall \phi \in \Xi \quad (17d)$$

The fleet size is given by $|V| = \sum_{\xi \in \Xi} z_{0\xi}$ and $z_{\xi\phi} = 1$ indicate the trip sequences.

While the structure of the optimization problem is very simple, the number of decision variables grows very fast, namely with $|\Xi|^2$. Hence, we implemented a column generation with a greedy heuristic to find an initial solution. Details can be found in C.

4.3. Traffic assignment module

The decision-relevant travel times t_l and link flows q_l on link l for the PUDO network design problem formulated in Eq. (2) are obtained from a lower-level traffic assignment problem given

- network configuration
- car travel demand
- AMOD travel demand
- PUDO frequencies (both curb and double parking)

We use a static, deterministic traffic assignment to address the strategic planning aspect of the PUDO network design problem, given the long tradition of using a static and deterministic traffic assignment in network design problems (e.g., Yang and Bell G.,

Table 1
Selected BPR function parameters for the PUDO network design problem analysis.

	One-lane link	Two-lane link
λ_v	57.05	56.00
μ_v	-0.05	-0.02
λ_q^{lin}	1,554.29	7,164.29
μ_q^{lin}	-1.75	-8.94
λ_q^{quad}	3,812.85	—
μ_q^{quad}	-14.01	—
v_q^{quad}	0.016	—
α		1.4
β		4.0

1998; Farahani et al., 2013; Bliemer et al., 2016). As mentioned in (A4) of the problem description, we assume that all vehicles, i.e., AMOD and cars, adhere to the same cost functions c_p on path p . Eq. (18) shows the function:

$$c_p = \sum_{l \in L} \Omega_l^p \cdot t_l, \quad (18)$$

where Ω_l^p is a link-incidence indicator that equals 1 if link l is on path p and 0 otherwise, and t_l is the link travel time. We assume that link travel times are determined by the Bureau of Public Roads (BPR) function:

$$t_l = \frac{L_l}{v_l^0} \left(1 + \alpha \left(\frac{q_l}{C_l} \right)^\beta \right), \quad (19)$$

In the context of the PUDO network design problem, it is expected that the levels of the design variables x_l and n_l influence the link performance function in Eq. (19) as they will affect the PUDO frequencies on both curb (f_l^{curb}) and double parking (f_l^{dbl}). The impact of stopping and parking behavior along urban road sections has been investigated, modeled, and integrated into German road design guidelines (FGSV, 2015) by BAST (2015). We adopt the logic of their method to accommodate PUDO activities in the link performance function by making the parameters v_l^0 and C_l dependent on the PUDO frequencies as well as the design of the road section, i.e., a two-lane layout, where parking or maneuvering vehicles can be overtaken, or a one-lane layout, where the possibilities for this are limited. While BAST (2015) suggests using discrete values for both variables given stopping activities, we consider them continuous variables to avoid issues in the optimization.

To account for both curbside and double parking, we develop the method by BAST (2015) further by defining a composite measure of stopping activities per link, f_l^{eff} , that is a linear combination of f_l^{curb} and f_l^{dbl} , where doubling parking frequency receives a higher weight, $\kappa > 1$, as it has a stronger impact on traffic flow. We set $\kappa = 1.3$ and provide a sensitivity analysis on the impacts of this parameter in D.

$$f_l^{eff} = f_l^{curb} + \kappa f_l^{dbl} \quad (20)$$

To account for the interaction between PUDO frequency and link length, we normalize the composite stopping-activity measure per hundred meters (\hat{f}_l^{eff}). We then interpolate the discrete values by fitting various functional forms to the data. We use linear models for the free-flow speed $v_l^0(\hat{f}_l^{eff})$:

$$v_l^0(\hat{f}_l^{eff}) = \lambda_v + \mu_v \hat{f}_l^{eff} \quad (21)$$

where λ_v and μ_v are parameters of the relationship, i.e., the intercept and slope. Similarly, for the link's capacity $C_l(\hat{f}_l^{eff})$, we use a piecewise-function, for one-lane links (22), and a linear model for two-lane links (23):

$$C_l(\hat{f}_l^{eff}) = \begin{cases} \lambda_q^{quad} + \mu_q^{quad} \hat{f}_l^{eff} + v_q^{quad} (\hat{f}_l^{eff})^2 & \hat{f}_l^{eff} < 300 \\ \lambda_q^{lin} + \mu_q^{lin} \hat{f}_l^{eff} & \hat{f}_l^{eff} \geq 300 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

$$C_l(\hat{f}_l^{eff}) = \lambda_q^{lin} + \mu_q^{lin} \hat{f}_l^{eff} \quad (23)$$

where $\lambda_q^{quad/lin}$ and $\mu_q^{quad/lin}$ are parameters of the relationship, i.e., the intercept and slope, and v_q^{quad} is the coefficient of the quadratic term. We note that the intercepts represent the situation without PUDO processes. To incorporate the traffic flow characteristics of autonomous vehicles, we set the parameters α and β as shown in Table 1 based on a simulation study (Qiu et al., 2022).

The algorithmic implementation uses ‘‘Algorithm B’’ (Dial, 2006), implemented in (Lab, 2025), to accommodate the requirement of ultra-fast computation times of the user equilibrium in the overall optimization problem formulated in Eq. (2) (Boyles et al., 2025).

4.4. Upper-level optimization module

Typical ALNS applications, such as vehicle routing or crew scheduling, differ substantially from our CA-PUDO-NDP, requiring the adaptation of core ALNS concepts to our specific context. In conventional settings, the destroy phase removes a subset of elements (e.g., customers, tasks) from the current solution, while the repair phase reinserts them—often exploring all or a large subset of feasible positions. Decision variables in these problems are frequently binary (e.g., whether a route is assigned to a vehicle).

In contrast, our decision space comprises two variable types: a set of binary variable (x_l) indicating the double parking policy, and a set of non-negative integer variables (n_l) representing the number of curbside PUDO zones per link. Consequently, the definition of a neighborhood also differs. Here, destroy is reinterpreted as “unsettling” the value of selected decision variables: for x_l , this means removing the current double parking policy; for n_l , it means removing the current curbside allocation. The repair phase then explores the variable’s neighborhood: for x_l , both possible policy states; for n_l , for example, slightly higher or lower allocations of PUDO areas per link. Thus, the neighborhood of a destroyed solution is the set of all combinations of these individual variable neighborhoods that satisfy both link-level and network-level constraints. This definition of neighborhood reflects the key characteristics of the underlying optimization problem and offers an intuitive rationale for why two solutions can be regarded as close to each other, making them suitable candidates for exploration in the search for improved solutions.

Table 2 illustrates, using a toy network, the ALNS phases, the neighborhood concept, and the destroy/repair operators. In the first step, an initial feasible solution is generated, represented as a sequence of segments in the l - x_l - n_l space. This solution satisfies both the total curbside allocation across the network (30 zones) and the per-link capacity constraints. In the second step, a destroy operator frees certain decision variables, exemplified here by resetting x_2 , x_4 , n_2 , and n_4 . In the third step, the neighborhood for each freed decision variable is determined: for x_l , this corresponds to the two possible policy states ($x_l \in \{0, 1\}$); for n_l , it consists of values near the previous allocation. The overall neighborhood is then the set of all combinations of these individual neighborhoods that satisfy the problem constraints. As this set is typically too large for exhaustive exploration, only a subset of candidate solutions is evaluated, and the best-performing candidate is selected as the repaired solution (highlighted in dark blue).

We built our framework around Python’s ALNS implementation by Wouda and Lan (2023) and designed a portfolio of destroy and repair operators that leverage domain and CA-PUDO-NDP-specific knowledge. In the following sections, we describe the basic components of the optimization module.

4.4.1. Initial feasible solution

The purpose of this stage is to generate an initial solution that can be destroyed and repaired during the first iteration of the ANLS. This solution defines the initial region of the solution space that the algorithm will explore. In most ALSN applications, the choice of strategy for generating this solution has limited impact, as the algorithm typically moves quickly toward better solutions regardless of the starting point.

In our case, however, each iteration is computationally expensive, and the n_l decision variables are integer, not binary. This not only slows the overall search process but also delays full exploration of the range of n_l values for a given link. Consequently, it is advantageous to begin with a feasible solution located in a promising region of the space, or at least to avoid starting from an unpromising one (Blum and Roli, 2003).

To prevent the initial solution from triggering the O_4 penalty, our strategy to generate an initial solution allows double parking on all links (i.e., $x_l = 1 \forall l \in L$). Then, the total number of available curb spaces (N_{city}) is randomly allocated across the network links. This is done by initializing each link with its maximum capacity n_l^{\max} and then iteratively reducing the number of curb spaces on randomly selected links—weighted by their individual maximum capacities—until the total matches N_{city} .

4.4.2. Destroy methods

In this phase, the selected solution from the previous iteration (or the initial solution, in the first iteration) is destroyed before being repaired. The number of decision variables to destroy, $DV_{2destroy}$, is determined by the destroy rate parameter, which specifies the share of decision variables to remove. In general, this rate influences the size of the neighborhood and, therefore, the running time per iteration of the ALNS. In our case, however, this effect is less pronounced, as only a subset of candidates in the neighborhood are evaluated during the repair phase.

We implement five destroy methods:

- **Random destroy:** $DV_{2destroy}$ decision variables are randomly sampled from all possible x_l and n_l variables. This is an adaptation of a common strategy in classic ALNS applications.
- **Curbside destroy:** Destroys n_l decision variables for $DV_{2destroy}$ links (or as many as possible if fewer remain).
- **Double Parking destroy:** Destroys x_l decision variables for $DV_{2destroy}$ links (or as many as possible if fewer remain).
- **Network-vicinity destroy:** Targets a specific subregion of the network. The method samples one or more links, identifies surrounding links (either immediately adjacent or within a set distance), and destroys all associated decision variables. This focuses the ALNS iteration on refining PUDO policies in a localized area, where both traffic and PUDO operations can be jointly adjusted.
- **Complete destroy:** This method destroys all decision variables. It is used exclusively in combination with the “random restart” repair method (see Section 4.4.3).

Table 2
Illustration of an ALNS iteration for a network with three bi-directional links.

	Solution Space	Network Representation
Step 1: Initial Solution		<p> $x_1 = 0$ $n_1 = 9$ </p> <p> $x_2 = 0$ $n_2 = 6$ </p> <p> $x_3 = 1$ $n_3 = 6$ </p> <p> $x_4 = 1$ $n_4 = 3$ </p> <p> $x_5 = 0$ $n_5 = 4$ </p> <p> $x_6 = 0$ $n_6 = 2$ </p>
Step 2: Destroy Method		<p> $x_1 = 0$ $n_1 = 9$ </p> <p> $x_2 = ?$ $n_2 = ?$ </p> <p> $x_3 = 1$ $n_3 = 6$ </p> <p> $x_4 = ?$ $n_4 = ?$ </p> <p> $x_5 = 0$ $n_5 = 4$ </p> <p> $x_6 = 0$ $n_6 = 2$ </p>
Step 3: Repair Method		<p> $x_1 = 0$ $n_1 = 9$ </p> <p> $x_2 = 1$ $n_2 = 4$ </p> <p> $x_3 = 1$ $n_3 = 6$ </p> <p> $x_4 = 0$ $n_4 = 5$ </p> <p> $x_5 = 0$ $n_5 = 4$ </p> <p> $x_6 = 0$ $n_6 = 2$ </p>

4.4.3. Repair methods

In this phase, the possible values for each decision variable are identified and used to construct the neighborhood of the destroyed solution. The neighborhood is then filtered to exclude states that violate link-level or network-level constraints. We implemented five repair methods:

- **Random repair** [x3]: For each destroyed decision variable, the method determines its feasible values: for x_j , these are 0 or 1; for n_l , these are generated by adding or subtracting values from a predefined set, $neighborhood_{shifts}$, around the previous iteration's value, ensuring the result stays within the link's allowed range. Then, all possible combinations of these feasible values are generated and only those combinations that satisfy the global curb space constraint (N_{city}) are retained. Three submethods are used with different $neighborhood_{shifts}$ allowing the search process to move across the solution space with different step sizes:
 - Small: [-3, -1, 0, 1, 3]
 - Medium: [-7, -5, -1, 0, 1, 5, 7]

- Large: [-10, -8, -1, 0, 1, 8, 10]
- **Worst-congested repair:** Relocates curb spaces from less congested to more congested links. Based on the iteration's traffic assignment results, links are ranked by their relative travel time increase (compared to free-flow conditions) and double parking frequency. For links in the most congested half, candidate n_l values increase with respect to the previous iteration's value, whereas for the least congested half, they decrease. Possible x_l values are 0 or 1.
- **Forbid PUDOs repair:** Relocates PUDO activities away from selected links. This is done by randomly sampling one or more links and setting both x_l and n_l to zero, prohibiting any PUDO activity there. Freed curb spaces are randomly reallocated to other links with remaining capacity. This method encourages exploration of solutions where PUDO activities are redistributed from one link to the surrounding ones, improving the traffic state in the first link and potentially improving the objective (i.e., some AMOD users with origin/destination in a link walk to alternative locations in order to improve the traffic conditions in that link).⁶
- **Random restart repair:** Generates a completely new random solution, independent from the solution selected in the previous iteration, following the same procedure as for the initial feasible solution. This new solution is then immediately destroyed and repaired using the *curbside destroy* method and medium-sized *random repair*. The aim is to boost exploration of the search space, introduce diversity in the population of solutions, and avoid local optima.

In all repair operators, the size of the neighborhood is typically too large to evaluate exhaustively. Therefore, we apply two filtering heuristics to avoid exploring undesired states. First, we discard any state that has been previously visited during the optimization process, using a database of visited scenarios and their key indicators, updated at the end of each iteration. Second, we remove any state in which double parking is forbidden in a link where curbside spaces are allocated; forbidding double parking in such links can only make them either unfeasible (i.e., the $O4$ penalty will be activated) or will produce the same objective value as their counterpart where double parking is allowed⁷. From the filtered set, C candidate states are sampled, evaluated in parallel, and stored in the database with all relevant metrics. The destroy method then returns the state with the best objective value among these candidates.

4.4.4. Adaptive selection strategy and acceptance and stopping criteria

In each ALNS iteration, a pair of destroy and repair methods is selected. Many strategies have been proposed in the literature, most of them leveraging the “adaptive” principle, where the probability (weight) of selecting a method depends on its past performance. In this study, we use the *Segmented Roulette Wheel* method—an adaptation of the classical *Roulette Wheel*, the most widely used strategy in the field (Windras Mara et al., 2022). Here, operator weights are fixed for a predefined segment length, enabling different operator sets to be favored in different regions of the solution space. Destroy and repair methods are selected independently, so two separate roulette wheel selections are performed (Pisinger and Ropke, 2007). To further control the search, we define a coupling matrix that restricts the valid combinations of destroy and repair operators. For example, the “complete destroy” method is only allowed to pair with the “random restart repair” method.

At the end of each repair step, the solution from the current iteration is compared to the historical best. The current solution is then either *accepted*, and passed to the destroy method for the next iteration, or *rejected*, in which case the historical best is used instead. We employ a greedy acceptance criterion (*hill climbing*) that only accepts strictly better solutions. We also tested the popular Metropolis acceptance criterion (simulated annealing), which occasionally accepts worse solutions with a probability that decreases over time. This can help escape local optima and encourage broader exploration of the solution space. However, given that some of our destroy and repair operators are specifically designed to avoid stagnation, we did not expect this to be a major concern. In test runs, the Metropolis approach did not improve results and was therefore not used in the final implementation.

Finally, for the stopping criterion, the novelty of our problem meant there was no prior reference for setting a maximum number of iterations, runtime, or improvement threshold. Therefore, for each AMOD demand level—the AMOD module being the most computationally intensive component and the main determinant of iteration duration—we ran the optimization framework for selected N_{city} values over an extended period (> 12 h) and analyzed the evolution of the objective value across iterations.

5. Case study

We illustrate our framework using the Sioux Falls network, which comprises 76 links and 24 nodes (Stabler et al., 2025). Although this network is considered unrealistic for a real urban setting, it remains a standard benchmark in transport research. Since many links correspond to interstate roads rather than city streets, we uniformly scaled their lengths by a factor of 20, yielding street segments between 100 m and 500 m. Lane counts (one or two) were assigned arbitrarily, and PUDO capacity N_L was calculated assuming $L^{prot} = 50$ m per link. The original demand data from Stabler et al. (2025) ($\approx 360,000$ trips) generates severe congestion even without AMOD vehicles and PUDOs. Therefore, we reduced it to 25% (90,150 trips) to achieve a network average speed close to 50 km/h. The duration of PUDO processes was defined as 30 seconds and the walking speed v^{walk} as 1.5 m/s.

We set n_l^{max} for each link under the assumption that planning authorities would allocate at most 50% of the available link length (i.e., the total length excluding the protected section) to curbside PUDO spaces, in order to preserve capacity for other curbside functions such as parking, urban amenities, and public transport stops. Using a value well below the theoretical maximum PUDO capacity not only reflects realistic planning constraints but also reduces the size of the solution space, which depends on n_l^{max} rather

⁶ Note that this can also have negative impacts as the PUDO frequency in nearby links will increase and might violate the PUDO capacity constraint.

⁷ This is due to assumption (A2) and (A3).

Table 3
Overview of the experimental design with 33 scenarios, all with same base demand (90,150 trips).

AMOD Share (no. trips)	PV Share (no. trips)	N_{city}
1% (902)	99% (89,248)	{5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 89, 223}
2.5% (2,254)	97.5% (87,896)	{5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 89, 223}
5% (4,508)	95% (85,642)	{10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 89, 100, 150, 223}
7.5% (6,761)	92.5% (83,389)	{20, 40, 60, 89, 100, 130, 180, 223}

than the theoretical capacity. For this case study, we assume all links can take $x_l = 0$ or $x_l = 1$ (i.e., no restrictions on double parking on specific links). Under these assumptions, the network-wide maximum number of curbside PUDO zones is $\sum_{l \in L} n_l^{\max} = 892$.

As shown in Table 3, we evaluated 33 scenarios grouped into four AMOD demand levels: 1%, 2.5%, 5%, and 7.5% of total trips. Origin-destination pairs for AMOD trips were sampled according to the specified share and randomly assigned to any outgoing link of the origin node and any incoming link of the destination node. Given the VRP formulation, trips between directly adjacent links were excluded. We explored higher AMOD demand levels, but these generated excessive concurrent PUDOs relative to network capacity, triggering the $O4$ penalty even with double parking permitted on all links.

For the optimization parameters, literature reports a wide range of values for the value of travel time, depending on country, survey type (revealed vs. stated preference), trip context, etc. As a reference, in Germany and Austria VOT^{walk} has been estimated at 10.20 €/h (Schmid et al., 2019), 23.50 €/h (Álvarez-Ossorio Martínez et al., 2025), and 27.30 €/h (Kolarova et al., 2019), while $VOT^{driving}$ ranges from 8.30 €/h to 12.30 €/h for regular vehicles, and 4.70 €/h for autonomous shared vehicles. Assuming a fully autonomous fleet, we set $VOT^{driving} = 6€/h$ and $VOT^{walk} = 21€/h$. A large penalty value ($M = 999,999$) for $O4$ was assigned for each vehicle-minute of excess demand in a link.

Given the high computational cost per run, we conducted preliminary experiments across different AMOD demand levels and N_{city} values to set the appropriate ALNS parameters and identify the relevant N_{city} ranges for each demand group, as summarized in Table 3. A 10% destruction rate was set for the destroy methods, and the length of each segment in the *Roulette Wheel* selection strategy was 30 iterations. We run the optimization framework in the Linux Cluster of the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre, allowing up to 220 parallel processes per scenario (i.e., $C = 220$). We set a maximum running time for each demand level, ranging between 45 min and 8.5 h, for the 1% and 7.5% AMOD demand levels, respectively.

Because the CA-PUDO-NDP problem is novel, no established method exists for direct benchmarking. Furthermore, its characteristics make it impossible to determine the optimal solution without exhaustively exploring the solution space. Additionally, the objective value can never reach zero—objective $O1$ will have contributions as soon as there are travelers in the network—making it difficult to assess the quality of the solutions produced by the ALNS. To address this, we define two benchmarks for each AMOD demand level: the Status Quo (SQ) and the Lower Bound (LB).

The Status Quo represents a scenario in which AMOD services meet the specified demand, but no dedicated curbside space is allocated for PUDO activities and double parking is (implicitly) allowed everywhere. This “unregulated” situation mirrors how MOD services often operate today in many cities. Because double parking PUDOs have a greater impact on traffic than curbside PUDOs, SQ serves as a reference for a poor PUDO policy, and it can be loosely interpreted as an upper bound, although, strictly speaking, it is not: prohibiting double parking PUDOs in some links could still worsen the objective value by forcing AMOD riders to walk.

The Lower Bound scenario aims to isolate the effects of PUDOs on traffic from those of AMOD vehicle movements and fleet management. In this case, we consider all requests are served at their actual origins and destinations by setting $x_l = 1$ and $n_l = n_l^{\max} \forall l \in L$. In addition, the impact of PUDOs on the link performance function is removed by setting $f_l^{curb} = f_l^{dbl} = 0$.

Since SQ and LB define a single (x_l, n_l) state⁸, only a single run of the AMOD and TA modules is required.

6. Results and discussion

In the following section, we present the results of our case study, focusing on the convergence of the optimization procedure, the trade-offs between different objectives, the effects of the resulting PUDO policies on network speeds, and the relationships between link attributes and network configurations.

6.1. Convergence of the upper-level optimization procedure

In Fig. 2, we show, for the 5% AMOD demand case, how the best solutions evolve over iterations for different N_{city} values. Importantly, the runtime per iteration grows (as expected) non-linearly with AMOD demand: around 1–2 seconds for the 1% case, and roughly 50 seconds for the 7.5% case.

First, in all scenarios, the objective value improves rapidly within the first few iterations. After this initial phase, most cases converge asymptotically, often remaining flat for many iterations before a small marginal gain is found. A notable exception is $N_{city} = 100$, where the objective value stagnated for nearly 100 iterations before the algorithm escaped a local minimum and achieved

⁸ Note that SQ and LB are defined in a way that the $O4$ penalty is always null.

Fig. 2. Example of best observed solution by iteration for scenarios with 5% AMOD demand.

a substantial improvement. Although the predefined maximum runtime cannot guarantee that the global optimum was reached, the stabilization of objective values—and the consistent ordering of lines, with higher N_{city} generally producing lower objective values—suggests that quasi-optimal solutions were obtained.

Second, the gap between the Status Quo ($\approx 6,400$) and the Lower Bound ($\approx 4,950$) is about 1,500 units. The remaining difference between the LB and each scenario line (≈ 900 to 1,150 units) reflects the net impact of PUDO stops on traffic. This corresponds to an 18–24% increase (worsening) in the objective value attributable to PUDO processes, depending on the scenario.

Finally, for the scenarios displayed in Fig. 2, the analysis of the destroy/repair operators that contributed to improvements in the objective function shows that the *network-vicinity destroy* and the *random repair* operators with medium and large $neighborhood_{shifts}$ were the most effective. Nevertheless, with the exception of *double parking destroy*, all operators delivered satisfactory performance.

6.2. Trade-off between dedicated space and other objectives

Fig. 3 shows the Pareto frontier between citywide curbside provision (N_{city} ; objective $O3$) and the combined system objectives ($O1, O2, O4$)⁹. We emphasize that the total travel demand (private vehicles and AMOD) is identical across scenarios; only the mode split varies.

First, examining the LB lines for different demand levels, we find that lower AMOD demands yield worse objective values (i.e., the lines sit higher). This pattern stems from a well-understood characteristic of AMOD systems: for both solo and pooled services, higher demand typically reduces fleet vehicle-kilometers traveled (VKT), as vehicles make fewer and shorter empty trips between requests (Zhang and Nie, 2021).

Second, within a given AMOD demand level, the objective value consistently improves as the number of allocated curbside spots in the network increases. The curves are not perfectly monotonic, suggesting that some scenarios may have become trapped in local optima before the running time limit was reached. In real-world applications, where precisely mapping the Pareto frontier might be more important, additional N_{city} values and longer computation times could be explored. Notably, the marginal improvement from adding curbside spots diminishes: the first allocations bring substantial gains, but the benefit then becomes small or even negligible. A key policy-related takeaway is that, for the studied network, providing more than about 100 curbside spots offers no further advantage regardless of the AMOD demand.

Third, when comparing results across demand levels, low AMOD penetrations (1–2.5%) have limited PUDO-related traffic impacts—the gap to the LB (i.e., the “net impact” of PUDO stops) is small—and increasing N_{city} yields minimal improvement. In contrast, higher AMOD demands, with their greater number of PUDO processes, result in much higher objective values, and, interestingly, since the LB decreases with demand, the net impact grows even further. However, in these cases, allocating a higher N_{city} brings substantial improvements. For example, at 7.5% AMOD demand, moving from the Status Quo to $N_{city} = 100$ produces a roughly 12% reduction in the objective value. These findings suggest that, for low AMOD demand levels, authorities could forgo dedicated curb-

⁹ Note $O4$ is a feasibility constraint, as PUDO demand must not exceed link capacity. All solutions reported in the Results have $O4 = 0$.

Fig. 3. Pareto frontier between N_{city} (O_3) and the composite objective value (weighted combination of O_1 and O_2). Lower Bound (LB) and Status Quo (SQ) benchmarks are also included.

side PUDO locations with minimal system-wide cost, whereas at higher penetration rates, curbside provision can deliver significant benefits.

6.3. Distribution of curbside and double parking PUDO processes

In Fig. 4, we show the share of PUDO processes taking place on the curbside or as double parking across the whole network. Two intuitive patterns emerge. First, for any given AMOD demand level, increasing the number of curbside spaces raises the share of processes happening on the curbside. Second, as AMOD demand grows, the proportion of processes that can be accommodated in the curbside declines.

In Fig. 4c, the flat region—matching the maximum value observed in Fig. 4d—suggests that beyond 5% AMOD demand level, some critical links have already reached their maximum curbside capacity ($n_l = n_l^{max}$). Consequently, the proportion of PUDOs handled through double parking cannot be further reduced.

6.4. Effects of PUDO policies on network speeds

We now turn our attention to the link speeds across different scenarios, beginning with the network-wide average speeds and, then, with the distribution of link speeds for each case.

Fig. 5 illustrates the relationship between average link speed, AMOD demand, and the total number of curbside spaces N_{city} . As AMOD demand increases, average speeds decline, driven by the growing number of PUDOs and their impact on the link performance functions. Conversely, allocating more curbside spaces increases average speeds by reducing the share of PUDOs handled through double parking—consistent with the patterns described in Section 6.3. Overall, the results in the figure show that providing no curbside spaces and allowing double parking everywhere, as in the SQ scenario, can significantly reduce network speeds.

Fig. 6 provides a more detailed view of network speeds by showing their distribution. Comparing the violin plots for different AMOD demand levels reveals that higher demand not only reduces the average network speed—for example, in the SQ scenario, increasing AMOD demand from 1% to 7.5% lowers the average speed by almost 8 km/h, while the corresponding reduction in the scenarios with $N_{city} = 223$ is 5.7 km/h—but also affects the speed range. Specifically, higher demand slightly lowers the maximum speeds and substantially reduces the minimum speeds, which can drop by more than 10 km/h when demand rises from 1% to 7.5%.

When examining each demand group individually, we observe that increasing the number of allocated curbside spaces in the network generally raises speeds. This effect is minor for low AMOD demand but becomes more pronounced at 5% and 7.5% demand levels. For instance, in the 7.5% AMOD scenario, providing $N_{city} = 100$ curbside spaces increases average and minimum speeds by 2 km/h and 2.8 km/h, respectively, compared to the SQ scenario.

The net effect of PUDO stops on network speeds, estimated by comparing the LB scenario with the others in the same demand group, is negligible for the 1% demand case, but at 7.5% demand it reaches a reduction of approximately 7.5–10 km/h, depending on the value of N_{city} .

Fig. 4. Share of PUDO processes occurring at curbside bays versus through double parking, as a function of the total curbside supply in the network (N_{city}). For clarity, only the N_{city} values relevant to each demand scenario are included.

6.5. Analyzing dependencies of link attributes and network configuration

In this section, we analyze the best PUDO policies identified by the ALNS search for selected scenarios. Specifically, we examine the resulting x_l and n_l policies, as well as their relationships with link flows, speeds, and PUDO frequencies.

As a consequence of the second heuristic introduced in Section 4.4.3, the best solutions obtained from the ALNS require post-processing. In particular, we review the frequency of double parking PUDOs per link, f_l^{dbl} . For any link with zero frequency and $x_l = 1$, we set x_l to 0. This adjustment reflects the fact that, in these links, all PUDO demand is accommodated by the available curbside spaces, making double parking unnecessary.

Fig. 7 presents the resulting PUDO policies and their relationship with network speeds. Fig. 7a and b display the policies for $N_{city} = 223$ and $N_{city} = 40$, respectively. Intuitively, the $N_{city} = 223$ case assigns higher n_l values across a greater number of links. In addition, providing more curbside spaces increases the number of links where double parking is prohibited. This reflects the trade-off between objectives $O1$ and $O2$: since VOT^{walk} is significantly higher than VOT^{drive} , the optimization seeks to minimize $O2$ without substantially worsening $O1$. Thus, under low N_{city} values, more links allow double parking with none or only a few curbside spaces—ensuring that AMOD requests can be served without walking—whereas at higher N_{city} levels, double parking (which has larger adverse impacts on surrounding traffic) is avoided whenever possible. In both scenarios, there is only one link—located at the bottom right of the network—where PUDOs are entirely forbidden (i.e., $x_l = n_l = 0$).

Fig. 7c illustrates the link speeds for the $N_{city} = 223$ scenario. Compared with Fig. 7a, it becomes clear that links with lower speeds (darker colors in the lower plot) tend either to be allocated more curbside spaces (lighter colors in the upper plot) or to be completely forbidden for PUDOs (the aforementioned $x_l = n_l = 0$ case).

Fig. 7d shows the differences in link speeds between the $N_{city} = 223$ and $N_{city} = 40$ scenarios. Blue shades indicate speed improvements under $N_{city} = 223$, while red shades indicate reductions. The majority of links experience faster speeds when more curbside spaces are provided, with only a small number showing decreases. This results from the higher prevalence of double parking PUDOs

Fig. 5. Average link speed per scenario. Only common N_{city} values across all AMOD demands are shown. In the Status Quo scenario, SQ, $N_{city} = 0$.

Fig. 6. Link speed distribution by scenario. SQ: Status Quo; LB: Lower Bound.

in the $N_{city} = 40$ scenario, which alters link performance functions and subsequently affects the traffic assignment. Moreover, speed increases (darker blue) are generally larger in magnitude than speed decreases (lighter red). Interestingly, links with higher speeds in Fig. 7c tend to show little variation in Fig. 7d (their colors remain close to white), and these are also the links that receive lower n_l allocations in Fig. 7a.

In Fig. 8, we display the relationships between link flows, total PUDO processes ($f_l^{curb} + f_l^{dbl}$), and the resulting PUDO policy for two N_{city} values under 7.5% AMOD demand. Results are separated by the number of lanes, since PUDO activities affect one-lane and two-lane links differently. For one-lane links (Fig. 8a and c), we observe a tendency to allocate more curbside spaces to links with higher flows and higher PUDO frequencies (points in the upper-right region of the plots). An exception is the link at the bottom

Fig. 7. PUDO policies and link speeds for 7.5% AMOD demand under different N_{city} . (DP: Double Parking.).

right, where $x_l = n_l = 0$: flows are so high that forbidding PUDOs entirely is preferred to preserve traffic conditions, even though this worsens $O2$. For two-lane links (Fig. 8b and c), the pattern is different: most links receive no or very few curbside allocations, with curbside stops mainly concentrated on the highest-flow, highest-frequency links.

It is worth noting that the scatter positions across Fig. 8a/c and Fig. 8b/c are similar but not identical. Since both solutions forbid PUDOs only on the same single link, PUDO frequencies (vertical axis) remain constant. However, flows (horizontal axis) vary between the two cases: changes in curbside allocation and PUDO policies alter link travel times, which in turn modify the traffic assignment outcomes.

6.6. Links with forbidden PUDOs and resulting walking legs

As discussed in Section 6.3, when PUDOs are forbidden on a link l (i.e., $x_l = n_l = 0$), AMOD users must walk to a nearby link with available capacity.

Fig. 8. Relationship between curbside space allocation, the link flows, and PUDO frequencies for 7.5% AMOD demand. (DP: Double Parking.).

Across all AMOD demand and N_{city} scenarios, we found that every case except one included one link where PUDOs were prohibited. This outcome is expected: because walking time is heavily penalized in the objective function, the framework avoids forcing passengers to walk unless PUDOs on a given link critically affect system-wide travel times. The only exception—1% AMOD demand with $N_{city} = 89$ —appears to be a case where the search became trapped in a local minimum, as its objective value is worse than that of the $N_{city} = 60$ scenario. We expect that, given a longer runtime, a solution including a PUDO-forbidden link would also emerge for this case.

A consistent pattern appeared in which specific links were restricted. In all scenarios with AMOD demand below 7.5%, link (19, 17) was forbidden for PUDOs, whereas for 7.5% demand, link (20, 18) was selected instead. Link (19, 17) is short and centrally located; link (20, 18) is longer and at the periphery of the network. Both links have only one lane and were the one-lane links with the highest traffic flows in their respective scenarios. This suggests that, for the studied network and demand, forbidding PUDOs on two-lane links is not beneficial, as the traffic impact of PUDOs on such links is comparatively small.

Prohibiting PUDOs on these links required some passengers to walk to or from a nearby link. Averaged over all AMOD requests, walking times ranged from 0.07 min to 0.11 min. When considering only the affected requests, average walking times were between 2.5 min and 3.75 min, affecting 4.32% and 1.89% of all requests, respectively. Using the walking speed applied in the case study, $v^{walk} = 1.5$ m/s, these times correspond to walking distances of approximately 225–340 m, well below the average distances to local public transport stops reported in the literature (e.g. Tennøy et al., 2022).

7. Conclusion

In this study, we introduced a new network design problem: the CA-PUDO-NDP. After providing its general formulation, we proposed a solution approach based on a modular framework that combines an AMOD model with PUDO location and regulation constraints, a static traffic assignment with sensitivity to PUDO frequencies per link, and a metaheuristic upper-level optimization.

In the context of the worldwide expansion of (autonomous) mobility-on-demand services, this problem is both timely and relevant. It also speaks to the interests of multiple stakeholders, including AMOD users, private vehicle travelers, and society at large. Finally, we demonstrated the application of the framework on a small city network.

The proposed framework not only provides quasi-optimal results within limited computational time but also yields valuable insights into the interactions between the two key PUDO policies: the allocation of curbside spaces per link and the regulation of double parking. Our results highlight how these policies interact with link characteristics (e.g., number of lanes) and demand levels, ultimately influencing link-level speeds and flows. The case study further emphasizes the importance of explicitly accounting for the effects of PUDO processes on the traffic system, particularly at higher AMOD demand levels, where dedicated curbside provision can partially mitigate the negative impacts of PUDOs. For instance, for a 7.5% AMOD demand, providing 100 curbside spaces could increase average network speeds by 2 km/h. Overall, the findings suggest that, at low AMOD demand levels, authorities may reasonably forgo dedicated curbside PUDO areas with minimal system-wide cost. By contrast, at higher penetration rates, providing curbside capacity can yield substantial system-wide benefits. Completely prohibiting PUDOs on certain links appears beneficial for the system's performance, particularly on one-lane links with high traffic volumes. The resulting walking required from passengers whose origins or destinations lie on these links remains acceptable, as it is well below the average access distances to local public transport stops.

It is important to emphasize, however, that these results rely on several assumptions and were generated using a small, fictional network without extensive parameter calibration. Therefore, the conclusions should be interpreted as illustrative insights, not as generalizable policy recommendations. Moreover, our findings are not necessarily general AMOD properties, but they likely reflect the specific ride-hailing setup considered in this study. Prior work shows that ride-pooling can decrease fleet size, deadheading, and VKT, mitigating congestion—especially at higher demand levels. Thus, our study does not support the conclusion that higher AMOD penetration inherently reduces link speeds; the net impact depends on service design and demand conditions.

From a transport policy and planning perspective, our method offers three key contributions:

- It can guide policy-makers in determining a reasonable range of N_{city} values to allocate across the network.
- It enables the estimation of impacts on average network speed, given a specific AMOD demand and N_{city} level.
- Once an N_{city} value is chosen, it provides a quasi-optimal allocation of curbside spaces among the links.

Although the proposed model is static, in practice it would be sensible to solve the problem for multiple time periods to reflect fluctuations in demand (both in terms of trip volumes and origin-destination patterns for AMOD and private vehicles). This would allow different PUDO policies to be active at different times of the day or the week. For instance, N_{city} could be reduced at night to ensure higher curbside utilization, while freeing space for other uses such as residential parking or waste collection.

A clear strength of the framework is its flexibility to incorporate additional planning constraints, as decision variables can be fixed or modified to reflect policy priorities that are not intended for optimization. For example, curbside allocation could be limited on residential streets overnight to ease parking pressure, double parking PUDOs could be forbidden near schools to improve safety, or PUDOs could be entirely prohibited on specific links deemed critical by decision-makers.

The exact placement of PUDOs within a link and operational and tactical PUDO management strategies—such as those proposed by Stüger et al. (2022) and Vishnoi and Simoni (2025)—can have impact on the traffic flow, but cannot be directly resolved in our macroscopic traffic assignment model. However, our framework can guide transport planners by identifying the critical links, for which microscopic models can be built to optimize the specific placement of curbside spaces and the coordination with traffic signal control.

Our research has several methodological limitations that could be addressed in future work. First, regarding the overall framework, we assumed that the sequence of AMOD stops is based on expected travel times that do not necessarily coincide with those resulting from the traffic assignment. This assumption disentangles the VRP from the traffic assignment, thereby removing the need to compute an equilibrium. Although a numerical experiment confirmed the soundness of this assumption for a ride-hailing setup and for the AMOD demand levels studied (see Appendix B), its validity should be re-evaluated for higher demand levels and for ride-pooling operations.

Second, regarding the modeling of PUDO impacts on link travel times, we acknowledge that the lack of real-world data prevented us from calibrating critical parameters (e.g., the weight of double parking processes in the composite measure of stopping activities). Should such data become available, these parameters could be calibrated to capture the effects more realistically (and even capture traffic signal control and within-link PUDO location impacts to a certain degree). Importantly, the overall problem description remains general, and thanks to the modular structure of the framework, alternative approaches—such as different link performance functions or traffic assignment algorithms—could be easily incorporated.

Finally, for the upper-level optimization problem, we chose the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (ALNS) metaheuristic because of its flexibility and proven effectiveness in numerous transport problems. However, we did not benchmark it against alternative optimization strategies (such as Genetic or Particle Swarm algorithms), as this would have required substantial structural modifications to the framework, which we considered beyond the scope of this study. Furthermore, given the large number of possible combinations and the significant computational time required to solve a single instance of the CA-PUDO-NDP, we did not systematically calibrate or fine-tune the ALNS framework (e.g., the adaptive selection and acceptance strategies, or the parameters of the operators). Instead, guided by the literature, we explored a subset of relevant configurations in an informal manner. We therefore suggest that future research investigate whether alternative optimization strategies could outperform our current approach for this network design problem.

Future studies could extend this work by considering networks with different topologies and link attributes to better understand the role of structural features such as link centrality or free-flow speeds. In this regard, analyses based on real-world networks and demand patterns, combined with calibrated link-performance parameters, could provide a sound basis for deriving more generalizable policy prescriptions. Nevertheless, applying the framework to larger and more realistic networks may pose significant challenges, as the solution space grows exponentially with the number of links L . A natural direction for future work is thus to assess whether the upper-level optimization module can effectively navigate such exceptionally large spaces, or whether additional heuristics or modeling simplifications will be required. Another promising direction is the analysis of the effects of ride-pooling. In our current setting, walking is almost always detrimental to the objective; however, for pooling services, allowing users to walk to common PUDO locations could yield substantial efficiency gains, particularly if it helps avoid roads with low speed limits.

In this study, we have analyzed the advantages of implementing a PUDO network in terms of travel times for all travelers and the more efficient use of curbside space. Beyond these direct benefits, several additional positive side effects can be expected compared to door-to-door services or dynamically assigned PUDO locations. First, a static, predefined network of boarding locations is easier for users to understand and navigate. Second, designated stop areas can be equipped with infrastructure that enhances the level of service (e.g., shelters, signage, lighting) and ensures physical accessibility for users with mobility restrictions. Third, shifting more PUDOs to curbside locations could improve safety by reducing conflicts with traffic and providing better separation from motorized flows. Finally, for autonomous vehicles, a predefined PUDO network provides clear and standardized rules for where to stop—an otherwise challenging task that typically relies on human judgment. Moreover, fixed curbside locations could be mapped in high resolution, facilitating AV sensing and motion planning.

In closing, this work introduced a timely and novel transport network design problem aimed at supporting the urban deployment of autonomous mobility-on-demand services in an orderly and efficient manner. By doing so, we seek to highlight the critical role of PUDO processes and effective curbside management as mitigation strategies, and to inspire further research building upon our framework.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Chat-GPT 4.0 and Microsoft's Copilot GPT-4 for text editing purposes. Additionally, GitHub Copilot was used for coding assistance. The authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Santiago Álvarez-Ossorio Martínez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization; **Florian Dandl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization; **Allister Loder:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization; **Klaus Bogenberger:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Data availability

Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

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Appendix A. Notation

For reading convenience, we collected mathematical notations and categorized them in [Table A.4](#).

Table A.4

Notation.

	Math Notation	Short Description
General	$T = [0, T^{\max}]$	Evaluation period
	$G = (N, L)$	Street network digraph G with nodes N and links L
	R	Set of all AMOD requests
	D	Set of all private vehicle trips
	V	Set of AMOD vehicles
	S^P, S^D, S	Set of pick-up, drop-off, and combined pick-up and drop-off stops of requests R
	L_l, L^{prot}, L^{car}	Length of link $l \in L$, length of the protected section of a link, and stop area length
	t_l	Travel time on link $l \in L$
	t_{ij}, d_{ij}, c_{ij}	Fastest path travel time, travel distance, and generalized costs between links $i, j \in L$
	P_{od}, P	Path set between network nodes $o, d \in N$ and union of all od-specific path sets
	t^b	Duration of PUDOs
	v^{walk}	Walking speed
	VOT^{walk}, VOT^{drive}	Value of time for walking and driving, respectively
M	Large penalty factor	
Upper-level Optimization	x_l	Binary variable indicating double parking allowance in link $l \in L$
	n_l	Integer variable indicating the number of dedicated PUDO bays in link $l \in L$
	s_{it}^c	State (combination of x_l and n_l) of candidate $c \in C$ at iteration it .
	s^*	Best observed state
	n_l^{\max}	Parameter indicating the maximum number of dedicated PUDO bays in link $l \in L$
	N_{city}	Total dedicated PUDO bays in the network
	n_{od}^{AMOD}	Number of AMOD vehicle trips between nodes $O, D \in N$
	n_{od}^{PV}	Number of private vehicle trips between nodes $O, D \in N$
	$f_{od}^{curb}, f_{od}^{dbl}$	Frequency of curbside and double parking PUDO processes in link $l \in L$
	$DV_{destroy}$	Number of decision variables to destroy at each iteration
	C	Set of candidate solutions sampled and evaluated in parallel at each iteration
	AMOD	x_{ρ}^v
δ_{ρ}^l		Binary variable indicating the link $l \in L$, in which stop ρ is performed
B_l^v		Continuous variable indicating the start of a PUDO process of vehicle v in link $l \in L$
ω_{ρ}^t		Binary variable indicating whether stop $\rho \in S$ takes place at time $t \in T$
N_l		Maximum number of possible concurrent PUDO processes in link $l \in L$
o_r, d_r		Origin and destination links ($\in L$) of request $r \in R$
τ_r		Request time
$\tau_r^{early/late}$		Time window constraints for earliest / latest start for request $r \in R$ at link $l \in L$
Q_{ρ}^v		Occupancy of vehicle $v \in V$ after stop $\rho \in S$
ΔQ_{ρ}		Change in occupancy at stop $\rho \in S$
t_l^{exp}		Expected travel time on link l
q_l		Link flow on $l \in L$
f_p	Path flow on $p \in P$	
TA	Ω_l^p	Binary parameter indicating whether link l is part of path p
	c_p	Cost function for path $p \in P$
	v_l^b	Free-flow speed of link $l \in L$ (depending on PUDO frequencies)
	C_l	Flow capacity of link $l \in L$
	κ	Additional effect of double-parking on link efficiency
	α, β	Coefficients in BPR function
	$\lambda_v, \lambda_q^{quad/lin}$	Free-flow velocity and capacity without PUDO processes
	$\mu_v, \mu_q^{quad/lin}, v_q^{quad}$	Parameters further defining the free-flow velocity and capacity relationship to PUDO frequency
	$f_l^{cfl}, (f_l^{cfl})$	Composite (distance-normalized) measure of stopping activities per link $l \in L$

Appendix B. Demonstration of the validity of Assumption (A7)

As detailed in Section 2, our solution approach determines the sequence of AMOD stops (and thus the deadheading, solo, and pooled trips) using an expected traffic state with expected link travel times t_l^{exp} , which we assume to be independent of the chosen PUDO configuration. This assumption breaks the circular dependency between the VRP and the TA modules and removes the need to compute a full equilibrium, thereby substantially increasing the framework's computational efficiency. However, it is conceivable that under certain conditions the PUDO policy—that is, the spatial distribution of curbside bays and the prohibition of double parking—could influence the traffic state to a degree that the sequencing of AMOD stops, i.e., the assignment of vehicles to users, is significantly altered. Such a situation would introduce an inconsistency between the TA and AMOD modules. To assess the significance of these potential inconsistencies, we quantify their impact through a numerical experiment described in this Appendix.

To do so, we modified the framework in Fig. 1 of the manuscript to account for the circular dependency by introducing a fixed-point iteration, implemented as a VRP \leftrightarrow TA loop, which is executed until convergence. The modified solution approach is shown in Fig. B.9, where the hashed polygons indicate the components that differ from the main framework.

The fixed-point loop operates as follows. When a PUDO policy (s_{it}^c) is sampled, an iteration counter (eq_{it}) is initialized to 1. Using the expected travel times (t_l^{exp}) derived from the initial traffic assignment, we first execute a full pass of the AMOD module and then

Fig. B.9. Alternative solution approach of the CA-PUDO-NDP, considering the equilibrium between the AMOD VRP and the TA through a fixed point iteration (the hashed polygon in the diagram).

the TA module. The resulting link travel times (t_l) from the traffic assignment are then stored as the updated set of expected travel times, which serve as input for the next AMOD module call. At least two iterations of the loop are always performed. After the second iteration (i.e., once $e_{q_{it}} > 1$), a convergence criterion $\theta(e_{q_{it}})$ is evaluated recursively by comparing the outputs of the current and previous iterations.

This convergence criterion can be defined flexibly. In this study, we tested two alternatives: (i) the absolute percent change in Total System Travel Time (TSST), defined as the sum of all user—both AMOD and private vehicle—travel times from the TA module; and (ii) the mean absolute percentage speed change across links, given by $\frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \left| \frac{t_l^{(e_{q_{it}})} - t_l^{(e_{q_{it-1}})}}{t_l^{(e_{q_{it}})}} \right| \times 100$.

After verifying that both criteria led to similar behavior, we adopted the former for the results presented here. If the change in the selected metric across iterations exceeds a predefined threshold, the process continues; otherwise, the loop terminates, and the outputs from the final iteration—namely $\sum_r t_r^{walk}$, $\sum_r t_r^{drive}$, and $PUDO_{exceedance}^{cap}$ —are forwarded to the evaluation of the objective function. For practical reasons, we also impose a maximum number of iterations (set to 10 after testing). This upper limit condition is not shown in Fig. B.9 to preserve visual clarity.

We conducted a numerical experiment to evaluate the effects of including or excluding the circular dependency between the VRP and TA modules. Running the full CA-PUDO-NDP both with and without the fixed-point loop under identical conditions (network, demand, N_{city} , etc.) would require substantial computational resources; moreover, because the ALNS metaheuristic is inherently stochastic, establishing a clean comparison would be difficult. For these reasons, we adopted an alternative approach.

We considered four AMOD demand levels (1%, 2.5%, 5%, and 7.5%) and two representative values of N_{city} (20 and 89). For each combination, we retrieved from the database—described in Section 4.4.3 and generated during the case study in Section 5—all visited states, that is, all PUDO policies explored by the algorithm. From these sets, we randomly drew a subset of states for evaluation; the number of sampled states for each combination is reported in Table B.5. Note that fewer states were explored for higher AMOD demand levels because the computational effort required increases substantially.

For all experiments, we imposed a very strict convergence threshold for the fixed-point loop, ranging from 0.00001% (for 1% AMOD demand) to 0.001% (for 7.5% AMOD demand). We then executed the AMOD \leftrightarrow TA sequence for each sampled state, both with

Fig. B.10. Objective value with and without considering the AMOD \leftrightarrow TA equilibrium for the same scenarios.

Table B.5

Experimental design for assessing the impact of incorporating the AMOD \leftrightarrow TA equilibrium.

AMOD Demand	N_{city}	N. drawn states
1%	20	1000
1%	89	1000
2.5%	20	500
2.5%	89	500
5%	20	250
5%	89	250
7.5%	20	100
7.5%	89	100

and without the fixed-point loop, and compared the resulting outputs, including the objective value, TSST, link travel times, link-level PUDO frequencies, and related indicators.

The results of this experiment show that for lower AMOD demand levels (1% and 2.5%), convergence is achieved rapidly: more than 95% and 80% of the scenarios, respectively, converge within three iterations, while fewer than 2% and 6% fail to converge within the ten-iteration limit. In these cases, the objective values obtained with and without enforcing equilibrium are identical for most scenarios, and the differences never exceed 0.3%. These discrepancies stem from minor variations in the PUDO location reassignment of a very small share of requests (less than 1% of all processes).

At higher AMOD demand levels (5% and 7.5%), the situation is notably different. A larger fraction of scenarios fails to converge within ten iterations (38% for $N_{city} = 20$ and 19% for $N_{city} = 89$), and the objective values with and without equilibrium almost never coincide exactly. Nevertheless, despite these convergence challenges, the resulting differences in the objective function remain very small: in most cases they are below 0.25%, and in all instances they remain under 0.5%.

Fig. B.10 presents these findings graphically and highlights the overall limited impact of ignoring the explicit AMOD \leftrightarrow TA equilibrium on the computed objective value.

We conducted additional analysis to understand why some scenarios failed to converge. To do so, we examined the scenario exhibiting the largest differences in link travel times between the equilibrium and non-equilibrium approaches. In this scenario, the PUDO policy forbids PUDOs in two links of the network (i.e., $x_l = n_l = 0$).

Our analysis revealed that, for the vast majority of links, link travel times with and without equilibrium were nearly identical and remained stable across all ten iterations of the fixed-point loop. Only a very small number of links showed substantial variability, oscillating between different equilibrium points from one iteration to the next (as illustrated in Fig. B.11a). The objective value varied across iterations, but the differences were small (0.4%). A closer examination of the corresponding f_l^{dbl} and f_l^{curb} values showed a clear pattern: while the curbside PUDO frequencies f_l^{curb} remained stable, the double-parking frequencies f_l^{dbl} on two adjacent links, (22, 15) and (19, 15), oscillated in opposite directions (Fig. B.11b). These two links were located next to the links where PUDOs were prohibited.

This pattern indicates that requests associated with the two forbidden PUDO links were being reassigned, via walking legs, alternately to (22, 15) and (19, 15) across successive iterations. As shown in Fig. B.11b, in the first iteration PUDOs are redirected to

(a) Changes in link travel times across iterations of the AMOD↔TA equilibrium loop

(b) Changes in double parking PUDO frequency across iterations of the AMOD↔TA equilibrium loop

Fig. B.11. Detailed analysis of the five links exhibiting the highest travel time variability across iterations of the AMOD↔TA equilibrium loop.

link (22, 15), generating a corresponding traffic state $t_l^{\text{exp}} \forall l \in L$ through the TA module. When this updated traffic state is used by the AMOD module in iteration 2, the PUDOs shift instead to link (19, 15). Because the resulting change in the convergence metric exceeds the predefined threshold, the loop proceeds without reaching a fixed equilibrium, thereby producing the observed oscillatory behavior.

To summarize, our findings indicate that Assumption (A7) is reasonable for the conditions represented in our case study. In most scenarios, the objective values obtained with and without enforcing the VRP \leftrightarrow TA equilibrium are either identical or differ only marginally. When equilibrium is accounted for, convergence is achieved in the majority of cases, and the remaining non-convergent instances are driven by minor oscillations affecting only a very small number of edges.

As discussed above, however, higher AMOD demand levels and lower network-wide curbside supply (N_{city}) push Assumption (A7) toward its limits. This suggests that the assumption should be re-evaluated under such conditions. In addition, our analysis does not offer evidence regarding the validity of the assumption for other MOD configurations (e.g., ride-pooling), and future studies could assess its applicability in those settings.

Appendix C. AMOD module: heuristic and column generation for fleet size determination and vehicle routing

To speed up the solution of the optimization problem (17) with costs defined by Eq. (16), we developed a greedy heuristic and enhanced this initial solution with column generation.

C.1. Greedy heuristic

For the greedy heuristic, we created a sorted list of stops Ξ^{sort} by ordering all trips in Ξ according to the time of the last stop¹⁰ (in reverse). We define a slack time

$$t_{\xi, \phi}^{\text{slack}} = B_{l_2 \mu} - (B_{l_1 \rho} + t_{l_1, l_2}^{\text{exp}} + t^b) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where ρ is the last stop of ξ at link l_1 and μ is the first stop of ϕ at link l_2 . Then, we loop through $\phi \in \Xi^{\text{sort}}$ and look for the trip ξ^* with

$$\xi^* = \underset{\xi \in \Xi^{\text{sort}}}{\text{argmin}} J(\xi) = d_{l_1, l_2} + v^{\text{slack}} \cdot t_{\xi, \phi}^{\text{slack}} \quad (\text{C.2a})$$

$$\text{s.t. } t_{\xi, \phi}^{\text{slack}} \geq 0 \quad (\text{C.2b})$$

where we introduced a v^{slack} parameter to avoid solutions in which vehicles will idle at a link for a very long time before being assigned to the next trip. This would minimize the total driven distance, but increase $|V|$ significantly. The search for ξ^* will first run through infeasible ξ , which have an end-time similar to ϕ . Eventually, it can run into a feasible region; if it does not, ϕ needs to be connected with the sink 0. To speed up the process, we can also stop the search in the feasible region when $v^{\text{slack}} \cdot t_{\xi, \phi}^{\text{slack}}$ becomes larger than $J(\xi^*)$, and we can add $z_{\xi \phi} = 1$ to the solution and remove both ϕ and ξ^* from Ξ^{sort} .

C.2. Column generation

For our column generation approach, we first generate a limited set of variables $Z \subset \Xi^0 \times \Xi$. We build Z from the solution of the greedy heuristic and add $z_{0\phi} \forall \phi \in \Xi$ to guarantee a feasible fallback solution.

Then, we iteratively solve a restricted master problem (RMP), which is the relaxed version of the problem (17) with variable set Z , and use pricing to add new variables/columns $z_{\xi\phi}$ to Z if

$$c_{\xi\phi} - \Pi_{\xi} - \Psi_{\phi} < 0 \quad (\text{C.3})$$

before running the next iteration, where Π_{ξ} and Ψ_{ϕ} are the dual variables with respect to constraints (17c) and (17b), respectively.

We stop the iterations when no new columns are added to Z . Finally, we solve the RMP on Z , but with the integrality constraint active again.

Appendix D. Sensitivity analysis of the parameter κ

As presented in Section 4.3, the impact of PUDO processes on the free-flow speed (v_l^0) and capacity (C_l) of each link is captured through a composite measure of stopping activities (f_l^{eff}). This measure is defined as a linear combination of f_l^{curb} and f_l^{dbl} , such that $f_l^{\text{eff}} = f_l^{\text{curb}} + \kappa f_l^{\text{dbl}}$. The parameter κ quantifies the relative impact of a double-parking PUDO compared with a curbside PUDO. Intuitively, a value of $\kappa > 1$ reflects the higher disruption caused by double parking, as it temporarily blocks the carriageway.

In the case study in Section 5, we use $\kappa = 1.3$, as empirical data are not available and the purpose of the paper is to illustrate the conceptual framework rather than to derive fully calibrated real-world outcomes. Future work could estimate a more realistic functional

¹⁰ This approach works for solo and pooled trips.

Fig. D.12. Sensitivity analysis of the value of κ for scenarios with 5% AMOD demand.

form for f_l^{eff} , for example, through traffic microsimulation or empirical observation. Nonetheless, to examine how sensitive the CA-PUDO-NDP results are to this parameter, we performed a sensitivity analysis, presented in this Appendix. To keep computational requirements manageable, we restricted the analysis to scenarios with 5% AMOD demand and with $N_{city} \in \{10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 89\}$. Under the same conditions as in Section 5, we then ran the CA-PUDO-NDP framework for a range of κ values: $\kappa \in \{1.0, 1.15, 1.30, 1.45, 1.60\}$.

The results of this sensitivity analysis are displayed in Fig. D.12. As expected, increasing values of κ result in higher (worse) objective values. This difference is most noticeable for the Status Quo scenario (where $x_l = 1$ and $n_l = 0 \forall l \in L$), given the larger weighting of double parking for the calculation of f_l^{eff} .

The results of this sensitivity analysis are shown in Fig. D.12. As expected, higher values of κ lead to higher (i.e., worse) objective values. The effect is most pronounced in the Status Quo scenario, where $x_l = 1$ and $n_l = 0 \forall l \in L$, because all PUDOs occur via double parking and thus receive the higher weight of κ in the computation of f_l^{eff} . The influence of κ remains significant at low network-wide curbside supply levels, where a larger share of PUDOs still occurs as double parking. Consequently, improvements in the objective value as N_{city} increases are more noticeable for higher κ values. As N_{city} grows, the curves for different κ values gradually approach, reflecting the declining share of double-parking PUDOs. Indeed, we expect that the curves asymptotically converge, as beyond a very high value of N_{city} , all PUDOs occur on curbside bays, rendering the value of κ irrelevant.

Appendix E. Benchmark and performance analysis of the ALNS metaheuristic

The upper-level optimization module relies on a metaheuristic (ALNS), which does not guarantee global optimality. In addition to the lower-bound benchmark presented in Section 6, this Appendix compares the performance of our ALNS-based framework against two simpler heuristic baselines.

The first baseline allocates the N_{city} curbside bays proportionally to the traffic flow on each link, assuming that all demand is served by private vehicles (and therefore without PUDO processes). The second baseline allocates curbside bays proportionally to the number of MOD requests starting or ending on each link, that is, the number of PUDOs that would occur there if no $x_l = 0$ restrictions were imposed. In both baselines, double-parking is permitted on all links ($x_l = 1 \forall l \in L$). To distribute the integer number of curbside bays N_{city} across links, we applied an adapted version of the largest-remainder (Hamilton) method based on the chosen criterion (traffic flow or number of PUDOs), while respecting each link's capacity n_l^{\max} .

Fig. E.13 summarizes the numerical results for all demand levels and N_{city} values considered in the case study. Because the two baselines produced nearly identical outcomes, we display only the baseline based on the proportional allocation to link traffic flows to avoid visual clutter. Across all experiments, the ALNS metaheuristic consistently outperforms the baseline heuristics. The performance gap is small for low AMOD demand levels (Fig. E.13a and b), which is expected given the comparatively limited traffic impact of PUDOs in those scenarios. In contrast, for 5% and 7.5% AMOD demand (Fig. E.13c and d), the benefits of using the ALNS are more pronounced. As expected, the solutions produced by the ALNS and by the baseline heuristics converge as the network-wide curbside supply increases, since allocating curbside bays becomes less restrictive in those settings.

Regarding the solution variability when running the CA-PUDO-NDP with different random seeds, we conducted a numerical experiment for a representative scenario (5% AMOD demand, $N_{city} = 40$, and a maximum runtime of 6 hours). We ran 12 independent instances of the framework and analyzed the resulting objective values, summarized as a boxplot in Fig. E.14. For context, the figure also includes the single-run metaheuristic solution, the baseline solution, and the lower bounds shown previously in Fig. E.13c.

Fig. E.13. Comparison of solutions obtained with ALNS and a baseline proportional to the traffic flow.

This analysis confirms that the quality of the solutions produced by the framework can vary across runs. This variability is expected, given the enormous size and complexity of the search space, which may cause the search process to stagnate temporarily before escaping a local minimum. Despite this, the differences in objective values across seeds remain relatively small. Moreover, in every instance, the solution obtained by the framework outperformed the baseline heuristic solution. A closer look at the results after 3 h and 6 h of runtime shows that increasing the maximum runtime—and thus allowing a larger number of iterations of the metaheuristic—reduces the variability in objective values across runs.

Fig. E.14. Objective value variability for the 5% AMOD demand $N_{city} = 40$ problem with 12 different seeds.

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